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**Karinan de Sinukuan National Park – Integrating Wellness and Recreation in
Redeveloping the Arayat National Park for Regenerative Architecture**

In Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Subject
THESIS RESEARCH APPLICATION
And for the Degree
BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN ARCHITECTURE

Presented to:

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ABSTRACT

In the rapid approach of change and technology, there are things that grow exponentially and there are some that are waived and neglected which created a gap to people and their environment. Because of the busy nature of today's time, people are longing for the peaceful and natural ambiance of nature. This creates a demand for a recreation and wellness center.

This proposal aims to redevelop the Arayat National Park Resort at San Juan Baño, Arayat Pampanga into a Wellness and Recreational complex that may cater the needs of the people for rejuvenation and nature experience.

The proposed complex may accommodate different wellness activities such as different outdoor one with nature activities, health related buildings and spa centers. It may also cater recreational facilities such as pools, accommodations, resto, café and open grounds

This complex is also approached in consideration of regenerative architecture to bring light to the conservation concerns and issues of the development. Along with these are the data of different problems that affects the overall operations and performance of the complex.

This paper examined the different project considerations based on the project site and for overall, the feasibility of the project to erect

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

RATIONALE, SIGNIFICANCE & JUSTIFICATION

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

GENERAL AND SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

SCOPE AND LIMITATION

REVIEW OR RELATED LITERATURE & STUDIES

ARCHITECTURAL AND DESIGN CONCEPT

1. INTRODUCTION

In a fast-changing world, progress and advancement is very evident in the physical characteristic and nature of an area or location. Increase in number of facilities such as commercial establishments, skyscrapers brought by new technologies, and increase in transportation is an indication of growth for an urban development (Planning Tank, 2020). This growth and advancement in an area is beneficial in economic development as it produces opportunities and employment. On the other hand, rapid development growth strains environment and people because of the growing density of man and structures. A growing community or city can experience problem of overpopulation, pollution and stress towards people (Planning Tank, 2020). The relation between people and its environment is important as in some cases environmental factors impact physical well-being and even more on mental wellness by changing brain structure and function (Lindberg, 2023). In a growing community of bustling environment and most of the people are busy and stress, it is important to have a place where people can connect to nature and relax. This justifies the significance of wellness and recreation centers in the society. Recreation centers hold a vital role in managing stress and entertainment for the people in the society. This structure became an essential part of a community where people can interact, socialize, engage in different activities and relax (Ogunjana, 2023). Same as the recreation centers, it is almost always accompanied by wellness centers. This structures also holds an equal importance to the people because they both helps to relieve stressors of work and life. In history recreation became a huge part to people although historians do not often take consideration of this topic it will always holds an importance in today's modern world (Cymru, 2020).

In building this kind of structure where human activities mostly held, it is important to consider the effects of it to the environment. Use of natural resources, excessive carbon footprint, and environmental degradation are few of the evident effects of human activities. As industrialization occurs, more problems including climate change intensifies thus new approach in building structures are formulated. Green and Regenerative Architecture became a significant and evident trend for building structures nowadays. It is a method to counteract the plummeting environmental problems by adopting a more sustainable way of life that decreases or prevents additional consequences of human activities, especially those that pertain to construction projects (N.A., 2022). Although became popular in modern times, Green Architecture is not actually new for by tracking back in early times ancestors and early builders use sustainable elements that can be retrieve in the environment that are used wisely for human comfort with minimal effect to the environment (Hidayat, 2020). The growing concern on environmental issue raise the awareness of people to the need of green architecture and its significance for consideration in today's building construction.

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Mt. Arayat is one of the most precious gifts that the natures bestowed not only in Arayat but in the whole province of Pampanga. It homes numerous flora and fauna and provide natural resources to the people in its vicinity. With its lush vegetation, fresh air and natural cold water from streams and small falls, it is an ideal location for relaxation and recuperation for well-being of people. With the demand for a recreation and wellness center along with the existing project of Mt. Arayat National Park Resort in the skirts of

the mountain, this project aimed to proposed a project in redesigning complex for wellness and recreational activities.

The original Arayat National Park is a resort at San Juan Bano Arayat Pampanga, it comprises of small villas, commercial stalls, function halls, social spaces, amenities and pools that utilizes the falls and water from the upstream of the mountain. On the other hand, in spite of the current working layout and planning of the resort there are still a lot of room for improvement and could be change in order to improve the efficiency and use of land for the greater good. This improvement includes the uplifting of green elements for the sustainability and regenerative aspect of the development. This includes changing of layout of the current resort, materials that have been used and the different elements that's been utilized. In this project, the idea is to redeveloped this into a recreational and wellness center which will be called Karinan de Sinukuan National Park as the new version of the development. This wellness and recreation facilities will heed to the call of people for rest and rejuvenation. A recreation and wellness center for physical and mental relaxation that is away from loud and restless nature of the world. This may open up a lot of opportunity in many aspects such as of tourism, business and commerce and cultural presentation.

With this redevelopment, National Park will not be beautified and improved but it may also help to be more green and regenerative functioning of the resort.

PROJECT LOCATION

The project presents the proposed redevelopment of Arayat National Park which is currently situated at San Juan Baño, Arayat Pampanga at the foot of the Mt. Arayat. The project will remain and be developed in its current location as the site fulfills its needs. The site composed of flat to hilly terrain with a total of 73, 964 sqm.

or roughly 7.3 hectares irregular lot belongs to Parks and Recreation Zone as per General Zoning Ordinance of the Municipality of Arayat for years 2016-2025 under the ordinance no.28 series of 2017 of the Sangguniang Bayan of Municipality of Arayat.

Figure. 1.1.1

<https://www.google.com.ph/maps/place/Mount+Arayat+National+Park>

Figure. 1.1. 2

RATIONALE, SIGNIFICANCE AND JUSTIFICATION

1.2 RATIONALE AND JUSTIFICATION

The Municipality of Arayat as one of the progressive towns of Pampanga shows massive growth in infrastructure and economy. Along with technological advancement in town, it brought significant change in the way people live and affect the environment that they are moving with. In the reign of machines and technology, rises different challenges that concerns the conservation and health of town. In this particular time Arayatēños are eager to find solace away from the busy world, a place of rest distant from hustle and bustle of society. This project aimed to create an accessible and nature friendly space within the town for rest and fun.

1.2.1 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study may help in assessing the needs of people in communities of having wellness and recreational facilities. This project may provide the people a conducive environment for both wellness and fun in respond for the bustling environment of the society in today's time. This study may also heed the call of regenerative architecture that may be significant in climatic and environmental issues that the world is facing. This proposal may help the pre-existing resort and the totality of the development to lessen carbon footprint, lessen use of non-renewable resources, and maintain a sustainable functioning of the development with consideration for conservation and preservation. Moreover this study may create a suitable development plan that will most efficiently work for the land that will cater both its people and its environment.

1.3 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

From the past years, Arayat is gradually moving towards a competence and more developed town. The town continuously build new structure and infrastructure that aid the development of the municipality. On the other hand, this development creates a gap between nature and people as density of building continues to grow. In addition, streets and other public spaces became busier and crowded with activities. This provides the reason to have a space for rest and fun other than home that will provide tranquility and peace for people.

The existing Arayat National Park Resort is one of the prominent recreational facilities in Arayat as it provides pool facilities and accommodation. However, in the past years as Arayat developed, improvement was left behind. The project development does not yet acquire its full potential and there are much more room for improvement and expansion specially in sustainability and use of its land. This project aimed to proposed a redevelopment to Arayat National Park in terms of its use and be a recreation and wellness center approached through regenerative architecture.

1.4 GENERAL OBJECTIVES

The main goal of this project is to create a complete development that may cater the needs of the people in the community in terms of wellness, relaxation and recreation. Along with this is the goal to reimagine and revitalize the long-lost beauty of the project and approach it with green and regenerative architecture.

1.4.1 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- i. To assess the need of people both inhabitants of community and tourists in wellness and recreation to know the needs of space requirements

- ii. To study the topography and immediate surroundings of the project site to strategically plan a layout

- iii. To research vernacular materials and sustainable elements to be incorporated in the designs

- iv. To promote the municipality and create business opportunity to people
(maximize return of investment)

1.5 SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The scope of this project focused and only limited in redesigning of Arayat National Park Resort to be sustainable development and integrating it with wellness and recreation center. It catered different structure and spaces set out for one main common goal of improving the well-being of its end user. Among the structures are recreation facilities, such as sports areas, public and private pools and villas, picnic grounds and cafeterias, resto and activity areas. For wellness facilities, it includes several structures such as spa and healthcare facilities, wellness gym and other structures that will improve physical, mental, emotional and spiritual well-being of people which all be design in the light of green and regenerative architecture. This integration includes the assessment of people to their needs of spaces and also

considering the tourism aspect of the development area. In terms of Green and Regenerative architecture, the focus will be the layout, elements and new innovation to be included. Beyond this scope will not further be discuss and research.

1.6 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

RELATED LITERATURE

Wellness is an individual and active pursuit of a person towards well-being, a positive state that achieve by fulfilling the needs of oneself (WHO, 2021). Wellness is one of the active processes to attain a well-being state of an individual, a course of action taking consideration of health, socialization and happiness of the person. Well-being of an individual is very important as it encompasses personal performance that affects the everyday proceeding of the an individual. Similar to other state experienced by people, state of well-being is affected by different factors determined by social, economic, and environmental condition that surround a person. These factors target the different conditions of a person, from physical, mental, emotional and intellectual well-being. Wellness as a process to attain well-being must consider and focus on these different angles in addressing matter. On the same approach, Wellness and Recreation Centers that pivots the different wellness activities holds so much relevance in catering those necessity for well-being.

Wellness and Recreation Center became a trend in today's industry because of the growing concern and emphasis on mental and physical well-being of the generation. They became an avenue for people to achieve holistic health and overall wellbeing by offering quality environment and services including spa treatments, mental health

counseling, physical activities and social welfare (Ben, 2023). From the data provided by The Global Spa & Wellness Economy Monitor Report in 2014 the trend of wellness center spiked a 12.7 % increase from 2012 to 2013 that show \$103.6 billion of the total \$494 billion economy belongs to wellness and retreat centers. This indicates the massive growth of wellness tourism economy that shows the wellness minded consumer” with wellness tourism defined as “travel associated with the pursuit of maintaining or enhancing one’s personal well-being (Global Spa & Wellness Economy Monitor, 2014). Moving on year 2022 is another pivotal year for Recreation and Wellness center. Two years after a long drought of people for outside activities and socialization due to risk and danger brought by Covid-19 pandemic, borders and restriction lift up. This open up new opportunities for recreation centers to go back in operation. This does not only an opportunity to restart but it also open new discussion and approach in designing such structures. The pandemic event became a turning point for Architecture to think more critically for health and well-being. This phenomenon help architecture to equip new knowledge and practice healthy building with impactful solutions. This became the World Architecture Day 2022 themed “Architecture for well-being”, that also connected to the assignment of 2022 as the UIA Year of Design for Health in buildings and cities (Gattupalli, 2022).

Wellness became a global priority and recreation reopens after pandemic thus rise of Wellness and Recreation Center moved parallel with the growing demand of public. Wellness and recreation centers aim a one common goal of elevating the well-being of a person they offer quality services and environment that are unique and varies from one another. Philippines as one of the countries that has most worker and

manpower, wellness is much needed. There several wellness and recreation centers that operated to fulfill the demand.

LOCAL RELATED STRUCTURES

Lujetta's Garden Spa

Figure. 1.6.1

Top 12 Spa and Wellness Resorts in the Philippines: Palawan, Boracay, Cebu, Bohol.

<https://guidetothephilippines.ph/articles/ultimate-guides/spa-wellness-resorts-philippines>

A Wellness spa infused to the natural terrain and mountains of Antipolo. Commonly equate and compare to the famous Hanging Garden of ancient Babylon, this complex is surrounded by greeneries and decks to take sight of breathtaking view of Antipolo (Arcadio, 2020). This complex is also designed in approach of Green and Regenerative architecture with a Biophilic Design. This design is an approach to make structures and complex healthier not only for the environment but also to its inhabitants (Gattupalli,

2022). Lujetta's Garden Spa offers a quality service of outdoor and indoor activities, lodgings, spa treatments, pools and jacuzzi. It also has resto and event place that could be used for different occasion and gatherings. With its natural design and location, it effectively alleviates stress and help improve cognitive function.

Aegle Wellness Center

Figure. 1.6. 2

Radiant Good Health. <https://www.aeglewellnesscenter.com/radiant-good-health>

A luxurious beachfront wellness center located at Polillo, Quezon. This complex offers quality service including accommodation, wellness training, pools , beach activities and programs. This center offers more on health and physical needs of people. It was named after Aegle, the radiant Greek goddess of good health. This wellness center offers unique wellness program called thalassotherapy which came from the Greek word Thalassa that means sea. The site strategically located in beach front as this medical treatment used sea water that supply their pools with varying use of detoxifying,

balancing, soothing and energizing (Guzman, n.d). Aegle offer their place and service of rest and relaxation for varying lengths of single to week stay.

The City Club

Figure. 1.6. 3

The City Club. <https://www.cityclub.com.ph/>

Located in Makati's Central Business District. The 30 000 sq. meters state of the art amenities offers both wellness and recreation for the members of the club. It offers specialty restaurants, sports facilities, recreation, spa and residential units. This structure also registered under the United States Green Building Council rating system, which administers the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) program (The City Club)

INTERNATIONAL RELATED STRUCTURES

Internationally around the globe there are also several notable wellness and recreation centers that offers unique and quality service including:

GCSU Wellness and Recreation Center

Figure. 1.6. 4

GCSU Wellness and Recreation Center.

https://menefearchitecture.com/portfolio_page/gcsu-wellness-and-recreation-center/

GCSU Wellness and Recreation Center is Located at Georgia College's West Campus. It is a home for Bobcat Athletes (Georgia College athletes) from departments of Student Health Services, Counseling Services and the Department of Wellness and Recreation. This structure offers wide range of activities specially designed to the athletes of the school including fitness areas, aquatic, program and indoor and outdoor adventures. The building aims to combine the recreation, wellness and counselling of the students to improve their overall performance. The wellness complex includes multipurpose hall, gymnasium, pool areas, open fields, clinical offices, faculty, and dormitories. The design also follows the approach of sustainable building design including energy saving features from mechanical to natural approach of daylighting. Sustainable features like bio-retention storm water management, recyclable materials and a "super insulated" roof and envelope was utilized. Through this the building was

approved by the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) and achieved silver certification. (Menefee Architecture, 2019).

Rodos Palladium

Figure. 1.6. 5

Rodos Palladium. <https://www.rodospalladium.gr/>

A luxury wellness and leisure center infused with 5-star hotel located in Rhodes Greece. This multi-awarded leisure and wellness hotel consist of interconnected building which main structure is compose of six floors and five attached annex structures, one of which has a private pool and overlooks the enormous Aegean Sea and lush green gardens. Rodos Palladium offer a breathtaking view of the beach as all of its building were ideally located at beach front. The Rodos Palladium is recognized for its great display of service, great environment and amenities they offer from cosmopolitan bars, a sizable tropical pool, and a spa with an indoor pool.

1.6.1 RELATED STUDIES

Recreational activities either home based or community-based helps individual to stay fit and healthy. Spaces like parks, game houses and other recreational centers helps community to keep active, energized, and form a positive relationship with each other (The Impact of Recreational Centres on Community Development, n.d). In studies, recreation centers in communities helps to improve well-being. Having communal spaces and other facilities with the likes have been demonstrated to have greater health, a stronger sense of community. In addition, it is also beneficial for people to engage in activities outdoor, outside their homes and workplace. According to the research paper entitled “Outdoor Recreation, Nature-Based Tourism, and Sustainability”, recreation is synergetic and more efficient outdoor where people can connect to nature more effectively. Being outside in a natural setting was recognized as crucial for the improvement of social ties, human health and well-being, and reconnection with one's nature (Winter et.al, 2019). In line with recreational centers that elevate health and mood of people, wellness centers also tackle health with physical and mental as the main focus and more weight in consideration. Wellness centers are structures designed to help people in their health needs that contains different amenities to improve one self. Wellness center is dedicated in improving the health and wellness of the community. Recreation center and wellness center individually have their own specific goals but on the end of the line these two structures operate towards the same goal, to improve well- being of a person. This leads to discussion of interrelating and combining the them into one complex structure to cater health needs of a community. In the thesis study of Salonen T. (2017) entitled “*Promoting Wellness to a Rural Area through Recreation Facility and Programming*” the proponent integrates and include

wellness to people by proposing programs through recreational facilities to the community. The paper discusses that poor quality health care can be in regards to your physical health and refer to the lack of qualified providers such wellness structures. By integrating the two structures, it may create bond to people and achieve social confidence and wellness. this social wellness can be described as interaction with all things including other people and the world around. Social wellness may include being outgoing, friendly, and feeling affectionate towards others and our surroundings (Salonen ,2017). It is also revealed in the paper, that there is significant evidence that shows that participation in wellness programs and active goers of wellness and recreation centers has improved their quality of life and overall health, lower mortality rates, and reduces medical care cost.

RELATED STUDIES: INTERNATIONAL

A. Architectural Thesis: Wellness Resort, Tehri Uttarakhand, (Sonal, 2020).

Development and urbanization create a small but steady growing gap between people and their natural environment. This argument leads people to find a solution by architecture to minimize and bridge the gap between this growing matter. An example of this is the architectural study of Sonal (2020) entitled Wellness Resort, Tehri Uttarakhand. This related study aimed to create a development that focuses on nature therapy and biophilic design to aid in wellness and rejuvenation of people. Close to nature developments specially wellness related structure produces an adequate result in well-being of people. The synergy of nature and wellness structures create a harmonious environment for people that seek rest and retreat (Solana, 2020). In this thesis, they incorporate healing spaces to biophilia. Healing spaces as defined in the study is a place or space that speaks inner peace and total wellbeing. These

spaces were incorporated to biophilic design to relate to natural environment and improve the healing process of person's well-being. Including to this are the wellness spaces such as yoga and meditation spaces and rejuvenation and wellness spa that are listed in space requirements of the thesis project. As this study also classified itself as a resort, it also houses spaces for recreation and facilities for different activities. Nature trails, parks, homestays, camping lake, and cycling tracks are some of the recreational spaces that are included in the proposal.

B. Melbourne Community Recreation + Wellness Center, (Burnette, 2018)

Wellness and recreation centers became popular in architecture and in business world because of the recent global events. Growing concern in community's mental health and their resident's physical health give way in the rise of this kind of structures specially in the domain of our community. In the study of Burnette (2018), the importance of wellness and recreation centers as part of the community was given an emphasis. The study was to answer the problem of lack in facility of Melbourne for fitness and physical engagement that leads to obesity and wellness problem of people. Just like the purpose of this main study, it focused on catering the needs of community for their overall well-being. Melbourne Community Recreation and Wellness Center's priority is to provide a community-based space of multifunctional facilities as a sanctuary of health and fun. In the study, it proposes spaces such as pools, yoga deck, rock climbing wall, and community gym for wellness. For recreation and interaction, it proposed spaces like atrium, community hall, garden and parks. This study also adhered to principle of sustainability by creating this structure in light of green architecture.

RELATED STUDIES: LOCAL

A. Eco-Vernacular Therapeutic Resort: Reconciliation Between Human and Nature, (Canlas, 2014)

Resorts are one of the most prominent recreation and leisure facilities. They were designed with the principle of fun and enjoyable nature. On the other hand, they can also be designed for therapeutic purposes to cater relaxation and peace. In the study of Canlas (2022) entitled Eco-Vernacular Therapeutic Resort: Reconciliation Between Human and Nature, he proposed a resort that is close to nature and environment with imposition to therapeutic goal of the project. With the demand in resorts and other recreation centers as a place for entertainment, it sometimes neglected that these facilities are also provide therapeutic purpose. They become underrated in focusing their purpose for health and wellness because of the other demand for spaces (Canlas, 2014). To counter this growing concern, this study was conducted to endeavor a development that focused on rejuvenation and relaxation. The project site has been decided to be outside Metro Manila and not in crowded areas to focus on close to nature location goal of the project. This proposed study is set to create resort, hotels, spa, wellness clinics and other amenities that may aid the development move towards therapy and wellness.

B. Canlungan Nang Sinukwan Farm Resort, (Silva, 2017)

In terms of nature and great scenery, Pampanga, as home of a beautiful mountain and great farmlands, has a lot to offer. Aside from wellness resort and other related structures, farm resorts are also in the rise as they also give tranquility and overall, a

great experience to people. This study, as located in Pampanga, features great showcase of Kapampangan culture from the materials and design of the structure. The aim of this project was to provide a farm to table experience for the people visiting the resort. Along with this, the researcher proposed different facilities and amenities to cater relaxation and retreat. This project acts as a sanctuary and abode for people who seek retreat from the busy center of the province.

Definition of Terms

Recreation Center- a public space where events could be taken place, sports are played, and different activity gathering were held that everyone can be participated

Wellness Center- in its broadest sense, a wellness center is a place that offers health services for both mind and body.

Well-being- it is a state of health and happiness. It entails having a positive outlook on life, feeling content with it, finding meaning or purpose in it, and being able to handle stress.

Holistic- relating to or concerned with wholes or with complete systems rather than with the analysis of, treatment of, or dissection into parts

Green and Regenerative Architecture- it is a philosophy that promotes the use of renewable energy sources, energy-efficient design

Biophilic Design- architecture design aims to create buildings that are healthier not only for its surrounding environment, but its inhabitants.

Thalassotherapy- therapeutic use of seawater and other elements of the marine environment, such as algae, sand, mud, or the breeze itself.

Sustainable Building Design- Sustainable building design is an architectural movement that seeks to reduce the immediate and long-term environmental impacts of buildings.

Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED)- is the world's most widely used green building rating system.

Daylighting- daylighting is the controlled entry of natural light, direct sunlight, and diffused skylight into a building.

Bio-retention Storm Water Management- Bioretention is a popular stormwater management strategy that is often utilized in urban environments to combat water quality and hydrological impacts of stormwater.

1.7 ARCHITECTURAL AND DESIGN CONCEPT

Project objectives

- A.** To contribute to environmental conservation by redesigning a green and regenerative architecture (Earth/ Environment).

- B.** To create a wellness and recreational center that will cater the amenities needed to improve the well-being of people (People).
- C.** To create a landmark that will promote the site and also advocate health and wellness for the community (Site/ Municipality).

Design Objectives

- A.** To come up a layout and utilize design innovation that will lessen the use of non-renewable resources and lessen carbon footprint of the site.
- B.** To organize a complete set up of wellness and recreation facility based on the needs of the community
- C.** To create a visually and efficiently striking complex that will cater quality service that will leave a mark to the visitors

Design Criteria

- A.1-** To program and arrange structures that they will not block each other from natural lighting and ventilation, and provide them large fenestration.
- A.2-** To create an open court and call for proper circulation of air
- A.3 -**To incorporate skylights on buildings and create an open above structures
- A.4 –** To employ louvers and build structure on near streams and water for passive cooling of structures
- B.1-** To assess the needs of the community and incorporate it in the design.
- B.2 -**To provide common wellness and recreation structures like gym, pools, playing areas, deck and public and private spaces

C.1 -Fuse of organic forms and common design character of wellness and recreation for nature and mountain settings

C.2 -To use local bamboo and natural stones that are local from the site.

C.3- To make use of natural terrain and natural setting of the Site.

Design Considerations

- Sustainability
- Orientation
- Space allotment
- Function
- Building envelope and Fusion
- Accessibility
- Aesthetic
- Existing structures and Topography

Design Concept

As the structure will be erected and located in Arayat, the concept will follow the two prominent characters in the municipality, Mt. Arayat itself and Maria Sinukuan the Guardian Deity of the mountain. With this main concept, other micro elements related to this two are also used and incorporated to the design of the project.

CHAPTER 2

METHODS

METHODS OF RESEARCH

RESEARCH TOOLS

ACTUAL SETTING OF THE PROJECT

COMPREHENSIVE LAND USE MAPS (CLUPS)

METHODOLOGY

2.1 METHODS OF RESEARCH

This chapter tackled and discussed the methods that were employed to obtain the necessary data for the project. This section specifies the different dimensions and problems that requires data including the specific data collection method that was applied to obtain them. It also explains the sampling method that was utilized in selecting the participants that answered the different research tools for the data gathering of the study.

2.1.1 DETAILS OF RESARCH METHODS

This study relied in the methodological and systematic approach of gathering data that are needed to aid the development of the project. The proposed project explored redevelopment of Mt. Arayat National Park Resort with integration of wellness and recreation spaces that appeals for regenerative architecture. The aim of this project (refer to 1.4 General Objective) is to construct a conducive and complete development that may cater the needs of the people who will visit the place and specially, the needs of the community where it will be erected. To acquire the needs and achieve the objectives of this project, the study employed a mixed-method approach of both qualitative and quantitative. This approach enabled the study to have a descriptive understanding of motivation and underlying reasons and experience of its participants while investigating the numerical data for statistical aspect of the study. In gathering data, the study draws on both primary and secondary data to fill the information that demanded by the project.

Qualitative and Quantitative

Qualitative are non- numerical data that relies in descriptive explanation of the topic in exploring the different characteristics and insights about the project. To properly address the general objective of creating a conducive and complete development of wellness and recreation center, the researcher must understand the nature of a conducive recreation and wellness center and its underlying characteristic in order to properly execute the plans. This aspect of the study is the qualitative (descriptive) approach that will help in more in-depth understanding of the nature and needs of participants in the project. In addition, quantitative approach was also utilized to gather numerical data for the project. Numerical data that are expressed in graphs and charts helps the researcher to distinguish which has the highest numerical value and favorability to the different survey question that was distributed.

Primary and Secondary Data

Redevelopment projects are pre-existing structures that are re-utilized for the purpose of revitalizing and improving its overall performance. Redevelopments explore new ideas by assessing the needs of existing structure and what have already been utilized from its original plan.

This nature of the project justifies the demand of redevelopments of both primary and secondary data to be included and acquired in the study.

Primary Data - are first-hand information that are gathered directly from individual involved in the project. In this study primary data are gathered through interview and survey questionnaire that are distributed to the participants. These data will help to have

a comprehensive understanding of reasons and people's perception about the redevelopment.

Secondary Data- As redevelopment projects are pre-existing, they possess initial data from their original plans and other studies that might help in redeveloping them. Secondary data can also be acquired through other thesis, academic studies and official sources that may aid in contextualizing and support the primary data.

2.2 RESEARCH TOOLS

The research tools of this study were patterned and employed for the purpose of acquiring and gathering data to answer the specific objectives (1.4.1 Specific Objectives) of the study. The following are the specific objectives the study addressed and its specific data gathering tools and methods:

- To assess the need of people both inhabitants of community and tourists in wellness and recreation to know the needs of space requirements. **(Survey)**
- To study the topography and immediate surroundings of the project site to strategically plan a layout **(Observational study)**
- To research vernacular materials and sustainable elements to be incorporated in the designs in accordance to its environment. **(Internet Browsing)**
- To promote the municipality and create business opportunity to people maximize return of investment **(Interview)**

Internet Browsing

- (III. To research vernacular materials and sustainable elements to be incorporated in the designs in accordance with its environment.

Through the advancement of technology, the availability of information and data became readily accessible through different reputable sites and web networks. In this specific study internet surfing was used to gather data of the site where the pre-existing structure was located. Through this, different characteristics of the site and the materials that are suitable for the same kind of projects were also revealed.

Internet source:

<https://www.arayatpampanga.gov.ph/>

<https://www.traveltothephilippines.info/2012/06/04/visit-the-mythical-mt-arayat-national-park-in-pampanga/>

<https://www.forestfoundation.ph/publications/public-parks-and-open-green-spaces-guidebook/>

Observational Study

- (II. To study the topography and immediate surroundings of the project site to strategically plan a layout)

The project employed an observational study to collect primary data regarding the condition and characteristic of the site. As the project aims to redevelop the Mt. Arayat National Park Resort, it is necessary to conduct a site investigation to uncover the underlying issues and condition in the field particularly the areas needed of

improvement and development. Observational study is not limited in investigating the pre-existing structure that will be redevelop, but it also done in same structure with the same purpose such as the eco-parks, resorts and other recreational park. This is to submerge to the experience and integrate with the different activities and characteristic of a wellness and recreation center. Observation allows researcher to gain insights about the condition of redevelopment that can work together with participants reports through surveys and interview.

Personal Interview

(IV. To promote the municipality and create business opportunity to people (maximize return of investment).

This study employed data gathering tool to collect primary data using structured interview. One-on-one interviews were conducted in this study to gather a detailed insight from individuals that are directly or indirectly affected by the redevelopment of the project. Personal interviews allow the researcher to have a deeper understanding about the emotions, perspective and experiences of the participants of the study. In this context the researcher made sure that the data uncovered possible impacts of the redevelopment not only the psychological, social and personal concern but also the economic impact to the community.

Sources:

Tourism Department of Arayat

Business Owner Inside the Mt. Arayat National Park Resort

Resident of Arayat

Admin of Mt. Arayat National Park Resort

Individual Outside Arayat

Survey

- (1. To assess the needs of people both inhabitants of community and tourists in wellness and recreation to know the needs of space requirements.)

The study employed a survey questionnaire to gather primary data. The survey forms were designed to collect standardized information or data to the target population that are directly or indirectly affected by the project. This data collection method is efficient for identifying patterns, trends and overall attitudes toward the project. In this specific study survey questionnaire are distributed to reveal the attitude of the participants to different space requirements that are presented and the overall perception about the redevelopment

Target Participants and Sampling

The survey questionnaire for this project were distributed through google forms using stratified random sampling. The target population are divided into two categories, the participants that already **visited the Mt. Arayat National Park (50 participants)** and the participants who have **not yet visited the existing development (50 participants)**. The number of participants per category were both 50 individuals to achieve the minimum required participant of 100. These participants were divided into categories to gather data from the people who got the chance to experience the development for unveiling of different issues and concern and the participants who have not yet visited the Mt. Arayat National Park, to know the underlying trend and patterns to what they

expect in a wellness and recreation center. To gather the needed data, the following survey question were asked:

Demographic Profile	Municipality / Address (<i>Municipalidad / Tirahan</i>):
<p>Name (Pangalan) (Optional):</p> <p>Your answer _____</p>	<input type="radio"/> Apalit <input type="radio"/> Arayat <input type="radio"/> Bacolor <input type="radio"/> Candaba <input type="radio"/> Floridablanca <input type="radio"/> Guagua <input type="radio"/> Lubao <input type="radio"/> Mabalacat <input type="radio"/> Macabebe <input type="radio"/> Magalang <input type="radio"/> Masantol <input type="radio"/> Mexico <input type="radio"/> Minalin <input type="radio"/> Porac <input type="radio"/> San Fernando <input type="radio"/> San Luis <input type="radio"/> San Simon <input type="radio"/> Sta. Ana <input type="radio"/> Santa Rita <input type="radio"/> Santo Tomas <input type="radio"/> Sasmuan <input type="radio"/> Outside Pampanga
<p>Age (Edad): *</p> <p><input type="radio"/> below 18 years old</p> <p><input type="radio"/> 18 - 25 years old</p> <p><input type="radio"/> 26 - 40 years old</p> <p><input type="radio"/> 41 - 59 years old</p> <p><input type="radio"/> 60 and above</p>	
<p>Gender (Kasarian): *</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Male</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Female</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Prefer not to say</p>	
<p>Employment Status (Trabaho): *</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Student</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Employed</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Self Employed</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Unemployed</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Retiree</p>	

Figure 2.2.1

<https://forms.gle/b4VfvVzbuQt82XXu7>

Do you know Any Recreational and Wellness Center (Building or place that offers *
Wellness and health and other facilities such as sports, spa, pools, park, event
center, stay in villas, etc.)?

*(Meron ka bang alam na lugar na nag aalok ng serbisyong wellness at
panlibangan? halimbawa: sports facility, spa, resort with swimming pools, park,
event centers, villas, etc.)*

Yes

No

Do you know Any Recreational and Wellness Center around Arayat? *

(Meron ka bang alam na lugar na Panlibangan at Wellness sa Arayat?)

Yes

No

Have you ever visited and stay to this kind of building or place (Any recreation *
and wellness facilities)?

*(Naranasan mo na bang bumisita sa mga ganitong lugar na nag aalok ng
wellness at panlibangan?)*

Yes

No

(In connection to previous question) *

If **yes** please mark whether the wellness center is outside or inside Arayat
Pampanga. If **no** please mark never been.

*(Ayon sa iyong tugon sa nakaraang tanong, Kung Yes ang iyong naging sagot ay
markahan kung ito ba ay sa Labas o Loob ng Arayat Pampanga. Kung No
naman ay markahan ang Never Been.)*

Outside Arayat (labas)

Inside Arayat (loob)

Never Been

Figure 2.2.2

<https://forms.gle/b4VfvVzbuQt82XXu7>

What kind of wellness or recreation facility have you visited? Select all that applies *

(Anong uri ng wellness o recreation facility and iyong napuntahan? Maaring magmarka ng higit sa isa)

Spa

Resort

Park / Nature Park

Sports Centers

Other: _____

How often do you visit Recreation or Wellness Center or other similar structure like resort, spa, sports facilities, and leisure *

(Gaano kadalas ang iyong pagbisita sa mga pasilidad gaya ng wellness at recreation center at sa iba pang mga katulad na istraktura gaya ng resort, spa, sports facilities, at lugar na panlibangan?)

Frequent (Madalas)

Occasionally (Minsan)

Rarely (Bihira)

Have you visited the Mt. Arayat National Park (Resort) located at Arayat Pampanga ? *

(Nakabisita ka na ba sa Mt. Arayat National Park (Resort) na matatagpuan sa Arayat Pampanga?)

Yes

No

Figure 2.2.3

<https://forms.gle/b4VfvVzbuQt82XXu7>

EXISTING ISSUES AND PERSONAL EXPERIENCE IN ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK

Ang Section na ito ay para lamang sa mga sumagot YES at nakapunta at nakabisita na sa Mt. Arayat National Park. kung ay naging sagot ay NO at hindi pa nakakapunta sa resort ay maaaring ng i-next at sagutin ang susunod na section. Salamat.

Rating the Spaces
 In rating 1-5, With 5 being the highest. Rate your experience about the existing areas/ aspect of the Arayat National park
(Sa pag-grado bilang 1-5, 5 ang pinakamataas. Bigyan ng grado ang iyong karanasan sa mga sumusunod na serbisyo at lugar sa loob ng Arayat National Park)

Swimming Pools

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

Utilities (Shower and Toilet)

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

Cottages

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

Stay-in Rooms

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

Event Center

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

Food Stalls

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

Parking and Transportation

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

Other Attractions (Fish Ponds and 100 steps)

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

What do you like about your experience in Arayat National Park? Mark all that applies

(Ano ang iyong nagustuhan sa iyong pagbisita sa Mt. Arayat National Park? Maaaring pumili ng higit sa isa)

- Close nature/ environment
- Ambiance
- Service
- Design of structures
- Facilities
- Food
- Transportation / easy access to location
- Other: _____

What do you think the areas/aspect that are needed of improvement?

(Ano sa iyong palagay ang nangangailangan pang paunladin at pag inamin sa Mt. Arayat National Park?)

Your answer _____

If the Arayat National park will be redevelop, what spaces/activities would you like to see in the redevelopment? Check all that applies

(Kung ire-redevelop ang Arayat National Park ano ang mga spaces o establisimiyento ang gusto mong makita? Maaaring pumili ng higit sa isa)

- Café and resto
- Parks and playgrounds
- Activity and Interactive area
- Food Park
- Additional Villas and cottages
- Sports facilities
- Spa and wellness
- Other: _____

Figure 2.2.4 <https://forms.gle/b4VfvVzbuQt82XXu7>

Space Suggestions	Favorability and People Perception
<p>In seeking for Recreation and Wellness Center. What interest you in visiting such structure? Select all that applies *</p> <p><i>(Sa pagpili ng pupuntahang Recreation at Wellness Center. Ano ang mga iyong tintingnan at hinahanap? Maaaring pumili ng higit sa isa)</i></p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Ambiance <input type="checkbox"/> Location <input type="checkbox"/> Offered Facilities <input type="checkbox"/> Food <input type="checkbox"/> Villas <input type="checkbox"/> Transportation <input type="checkbox"/> Aesthetics (Design of Structure) <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____ </p>	<p>If the current Arayat National Park will be redeveloped and redesign to maximize its Green Aspect (lessen the damage to environment through Green Architecture) and cater Recreational and Wellness Facility (Spa, sports, resort, event center, leisure activities). Would you approved and more interested to visit and support it? *</p> <p><i>(Kung ire-redevelop ang Arayat National Park upang maging Wellness and Recreation Center at mapaunlad ito sa paglilinang at konserbasyon ng kalikasan. Sang- ayon kaba dito at susuportahan mo ba ito?)</i></p> <p> <input type="radio"/> Strongly Approved (Malakas na Sumasang-Ayon) <input type="radio"/> Approved (Sang-Ayon) <input type="radio"/> Somehow Approved (Kahit Papaano ay Sang-Ayon) <input type="radio"/> Not Approved (Hindi Sang-Ayon) </p>
<p>In seeking for Recreation and Wellness Center. What specific spaces / facilities you are looking for? Select all that applies *</p> <p><i>(Sa pagpili ng pupuntahang Recreation and Wellness Center. Anu-ano ang mga serbisyo at spaces na iyong hinahanap? Maaaring pumili ng higit sa isa.)</i></p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Café and resto <input type="checkbox"/> Parks and playgrounds <input type="checkbox"/> Activity and Interactive area <input type="checkbox"/> Food Park <input type="checkbox"/> Villas and cottages <input type="checkbox"/> Sports facilities <input type="checkbox"/> Spa and wellness <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____ </p>	<p>Do you think it would be beneficial to Arayat and its residents to redevelop and redesign the Arayat National Park into more green and sustaining Recreation and Wellness Center? *</p> <p><i>(Sa iyong palagay, Makakabuti ba sa Arayat at kanyang mga residente ang pag re-redevelop ng Arayat National Park bilang isang Wellness and Recreation center na naglalayong mapabuti ang antas nito sa pagiging makakalikasan?)</i></p> <p> <input type="radio"/> Yes <input type="radio"/> No </p>
	<p>What do you think is the relevance of building wellness and recreation that are also sustainable and close to environment? *</p> <p><i>(Ano sa iyong palagay ang kahalagahan ng pagtatayo ng wellness and recreation center na sustainable at malapit sa kalikasan?)</i></p> <p>Your answer _____</p>

Figure 2.2.5

<https://forms.gle/b4VfvVzbuQt82XXu7>

2.3 ACTUAL SETTING OF PROJECT

A. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The proposed project is a redevelopment of Mt. Arayat National Park Resort, an existing resort that cater amenities such as public pools, event areas and several rooms and lodgings for day and overnight stays. The proposed redevelopment will transform this resort into a wellness and recreational park that includes spaces to elevates one's mood, health and well-being.

B. PROPONENT/S

Figure 2.3.1 Arayat LGU Logo

The Mt. Arayat National Park Resort is under the management of Local Government Unit of Arayat. For the past years, the operations including repairs and renovations of the Mt. Arayat National Park have been done by LGU of Arayat. For this project, Arayat Local Government Unit are willing to support the redevelopment of Mt. Arayat National Park.

Partners

Department of Tourism (DOT)

Figure 2.3.2 Department of Tourism Logo

DOT endeavors a sustainable, resilient and competitive tourism in the Philippines. Along with this goal, it recognizes ecosystem-based tourism that showcase the beautiful topography and natural characteristic of the different tourist spot in the country. The department aims to support and promote sustainable management and development for this kind of projects.

Asian Development Bank

Figure 2.3.3 ADB Logo

Asian Development Bank, as a multilateral development bank, has given attention and support to the development of tourism in South-East Asia. It has provided technical and financial assistance to boost sustainable tourism after the Covid-19 pandemic. It

catalyzes private financing to support local tourism business and revive the tourism in the country.

2.3.1 SITE PROFILE AND ANALYSIS

The pre-existed park is situated at San Juan Baño, Arayat Pampanga, the project site is well suitable for wellness and recreation as it presents a calm and serene environment that is close to nature. The natural character of the location, having a lot of greeneries and amazing topography of Mt. Arayat, benefits the character and ambiance of a conducive wellness and recreation area. The site is composed of flat to hilly terrain with a total lot area of 73,964 sqm. or roughly 7.3 hectares irregular lot that belongs to Parks and Recreation Zone as per General Zoning Ordinance of Municipality of Arayat years 2016-2025 under the ordinance no. 28 series of 2017 of the Sangguniang Bayan of Municipality of Arayat.

The proposed location for the project belongs to the eco-tourism district of the land use plan of Arayat, it has several residential areas which are the primary visitor of the current development. The surrounding areas and barangays are composed mostly of Agricultural Production that makes the site greener and calmer in nature. The national highway and the central business district of Arayat is relatively close but has enough distance not to cause disturbance to the site. These surrounding areas create an efficient

balance of tranquility away from noise of the world but still propose accessibility for other commercial and business district near the site.

1. PHYSICAL PROFILE OF THE SITE

a. Geographical Location

Arayat is situated at northern-eastern portion of Pampanga. The Municipality is bounded by Magalang, Candaba by north and Sta. Ana by south. On another portion, it was bounded by Mexico on west and Cabiao Nueva Ecija by east. The actual project site at San Juan Baño, Arayat Pampanga is 2km away and approximately 5 minutes travel from the fork road of main highway going to Nueva Ecija.

b. Topography

The site is composed of flat to hilly terrain adjacent to the Mt. Arayat. The main attraction of Arayat is the twin-peak of the mountain with peak no.1 having a towering height of 986 meters above sea level and peak no. 2 of a height of 1026 meters above sea level.

c. Climatic Condition

The prevailing climate of Arayat listed under the category of type 1 climate based on the Modified Coronas Climate Map of the Philippines (PAGASA). In this type of climate, the region consists of two prevalent seasons, the dry that start on December and ends in May and the wet season from June to September.

d. Soil Classification

Arayat Soil Classification mostly belong to clay loam and sandy loam soil.

2. PLANNING DATA AND SUPPLY SYSTEMS

Province: Pampanga

Region: III

Municipality: Arayat

Barangay: San Juan Baño

a. Power and Energy Sources

Arayat power and energy supply are both under the coverage of Pampanga I Electric Cooperative (PELCO 1). According to Pampanga I Electric Cooperative (PELCO 1) of Arayat Area Office, the total of power circuits in Arayat is 332.818 kilometers with a capacity of 10MVA and has a present load of 81%.

b. Water supply

The water supply of the site is mainly by natural springs and falls in the mountains while supported by BCBI WATERWORKS ARAYAT BRANCH INC.

c. Telecommunications

There are four telecommunication systems that operates in Arayat namely DIGITAL, GLOBE, AIR CABLE, CONVERGE.

d. Road Network

The national highway connecting to the site is the Jose Abad Santos Avenue (JASA). This highway is connected by the minor road of Mt. Arayat National Park Road which is 2 km away from the actual project site.

3. LOT BEARINGS

LOT 1. PSU-154155		
LINES	BEARINGS	DISTANCES
1-2	N 60°37' W	22.19 m
2-3	S 83°10' E	69.21 m
3-4	N 21°17' E	42.30 m
4-5	S 67°11' E	33.12 m
5-6	S 47°24' E	18.72 m
6-7	S 02°13' W	13.67 m
7-8	N 67°16' E	16.99 m
8-9	S 82°45' E	32.43 m
9-10	N 02°53' E	6.30 m
10-11	S 83°04' E	56.07 m
11-12	N 06°26' E	31.72 m
12-13	S 80°23' E	65.52 m
13-14	S 18°20' E	32.89 m
14-15	S 31°35' E	32.60 m
15-16	S 54°46' E	65.67 m
16-17	S 88° 18' W	122.52 m
17-18	S 23°01' W	28.95 m
18-19	S 30°01' W	11.41 m
19-20	S 15°48' W	31.70 m
20-21	S 08°05' E	12.72 m
21-22	S 16°51' W	37.56 m
22-23	S 05°03' W	37.96 m

23-24	S 74°41' W	8.52 m
24-25	S 72°04' W	3.75 m
25-26	S 19°40' W	7.16 m
26-27	S 53°58' W	11.92 m
27-28	S 11°01' W	8.38 m
28-29	S 03°48' E	10.46 m
29-30	S 31°35' E	9.31 m
30-31	S 20°10' E	7.34 m
31-32	S 54°23' W	5.91 m
32-33	S 52°12' E	31.31 m
33-34	S 31°37' W	9.10 m
34-35	S 41°31' W	29.17 m
35-36	N 42°42' W	157.88 m
36-37	N 61°39' E	31.64 m
37-38	N 52°33' W	59.91 m
38-39	S 51°25' W	2.66 m
39-40	N 27°04' W	15.07 m
40-41	N 35°34' W	65.62 m
41-42	N 19°16' E	33.63 m
42-43	N 27°03' E	76.94 m
43-44	N 81°45' W	53.87 m
44-45	S 07°41' E	12.87 m
45-46	S 86°58' W	25.36 m
46-1	N 06°30' W	29.65 m
TIE LINE: S57°49' W, 1151.21 m FROM BBM 33; ARAYAT CAD TO CORNER NO.11		

Table 2.3.1 Lot Bearings

4. Site Features

a Vicinity Map

Figure 2.3.4 <https://www.google.com/maps>

San Juan Baño where the site is located is one of the barangays that are closest to the mountain. In the northern and western portion of the lot are areas that were occupied by thick vegetation that helps freshen up air and passively cool the site. At the eastern part of the lot, the nearest area that is located are the residential area for the people of San Juan Baño. Further away in the eastern side are San Agustin Norte and Camba where lands are also occupied for agriculture and residential area. The road along the Camba going to the east is also the main highway going to San Vicente, Nueva Ecija, the nearest part of Nueva Ecija to Arayat. The vicinity at the southern portion of the site is intended for Agricultural Production. Moving further to the south is the town proper of Arayat where mostly of institutional structures are erected including the Central Business District of Arayat.

b. Road Map

Figure 2.3.5

Retrieved from: Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

TRAVEL TIME AND DISTANCE FROM OTHER TOWNS (END USERS)

Town Center (End User)	Approximate Time Travel	Approximate Distance from the Project
Angeles	55 min	26.5 km
Apalit	56 min	26.5 km
Bacolor	1hr 9 min	38.5 km
Candaba	59 min	24.4 km
Floridablanca	1hr 29 min	74.3 km
Guagua	1hr 13 min	40.4 km
Lubao	1hr 28 min	55.9 km

Mabalacat	1hr	31.4 km
Macabebe	1hr 43 min	39.3 km
Magalang	52 min	24.2 km
Masantol	1hr 43 min	40.5 km
Mexico	50 min	23 km
Minalin	1hr 17 min	32.1 km
Porac	1hr 33 min	48.8 km
San Fernando	57 min	26.7 km
San Luis	57 min	22.5 km
San Simon	1hr 1 min	23.7 km
Sta. Ana	25 min	7.6 km
Sta. Rita	1hr 17 min	33.5 km
Sasmuan	1hr 27 min	53.5 km
Sto. Tomas	53 min	22.6 km
Metro Manila	1hr 46 min	76.8 km
Nueva Ecija	14 min	7.2 km

Table 2.3.2

EXISTING RELATED PROJECTS IN PAMPANGA AND THEIR APPROXIMATE DISTANCE FROM THE PROJECT

Parks	Location	Approximate Travel Time	Approximate Distance
Lubao Bamboo Hub and Eco-Park	Lubao	1hr 49 mins	45.7 km
Gintung PakPak Eco Park	Arayat	40 min	16.1 km

Table 2.3.3

Land Transportation

Provincial Bus Carrier (First North Luzon, RJ Express and Arayat Express) With trips from Manila to Cabanatuan and vice versa. Jeepney and Tricycles are also available in the vicinity of the site.

c. Sun Path

Figure 2.3.6 Sun Path

5. The Site

Figure 2.3.7 Existing Parking

Figure 2.3.8 Commercial

Figure 2.3.9 Entrance Patio

Figure 2.3.10 Open Area

Figure 2.3.11 Stalls and Tables

Figure 2.3.12 Play Ground

Figure 2.3.13

Figure 2.3.14

Figure 2.3.15

Figure 2.3.16

6. Site Justification

Positive:

- The site belongs to Parks and Recreation Zone of Arayat and Ecotourism District that befits the character and location of the intended use for redevelopment of wellness and recreation complex.
- It is 5 mins away from national highway of Jose Abad Santos Avenue that makes it more accessible for public but still have a considerable distance from the noise of the main road.
- The site is full of vegetation and natural resources
- It is not prone in flooding because of the high elevation where it is located.

Negative:

- It has a moderate vulnerability for landslide

Figure 2.3.17 Tourism Map

7. Legal

TAX DECLARATION OF REAL PROPERTY

TD No.: GR2020-02-0024-00752 Cancelled Property Identification No.: 019-02-0024-018-07

Owner: DE ROCES, ALICIA VILLAREAL M/TO ROCES, JESUS TIN: _____

Address: 1001 OROQUIETA ST., MANILA Telephone No.: _____

Administrator/Beneficial User: VILLAREAL, CARLOS M/TO CRISTOBAL, LEONIDA TIN: _____

Address: 1811 M HIZON ST. CRUZ, MANILA Telephone No.: _____

Location of Property: _____ SAN JUAN BANO ARAYAT, PAMPANGA
 (Number and Street) (Barangay) (Municipality & Province)

OCT/TCT/CLOA No. 343369-R Survey No.: _____

CCT: _____ Lot No.: 2 Blk. No.: _____

Dated: _____ Cadastral Lot no: 3116 "P"

Boundaries:
 North: NE: (ROAD) 018-09 South: SW: (LOT 3573) 018-05
 East: SE: (LOT 1, LOT 7, LOT 3) 018-08 & 11, 09 West: NW: (LOT 3123, LOT 7) 018-06

KIND OF PROPERTY ASSESSED:

LAND: **MACHINERY:**
 BUILDING: **OTHERS:**

No. of Storeys: _____ Specify: _____
 Brief Description: _____

Classification	Area (Sqm)	Market Value	Actual Use	Assessment Level	Assessed Value
AGRICULTURAL	73,964.00	87,530.00	AGRICULTURAL	20%	17,510.00
TOTAL :	73,964.00	Php 87,530.00		Php	17,510.00

Total Assessed Value _____ SEVENTEEN THOUSAND FIVE HUNDRED TEN PESOS ONLY
 (Amount in words)

Taxable Exempt Effectivity of Assessment/Reassessment: 1 2020
 By the authority of the Provincial Assessor Qtr. Yr.

RECOMMENDING APPROVAL: **APPROVED BY:**

 MUNICIPAL ASSESSOR Date

ENGR. ROMEO M. DIZON 06/26/2019
 PROVINCIAL ASSESSOR Date

This declaration cancels TD No.: PSP-020024-00743 Previous AV. Php 11,700.00
 Previous Owner: DE ROCES, ALICIA VILLAREAL M

Memoranda: General Revision.

Annotation: _____

Figure 2.3.18 Tax Declaration. Retrieved From Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

Zoning Certificate

Republic of the Philippines
Province of Pampanga
Municipality of Arayat

**OFFICE OF THE MUNICIPAL PLANNING AND
DEVELOPMENT COORDINATOR**

ZONING CERTIFICATE

To whom it may concern:

This is to certify that the following lot is located in Brgy. San Juan Baño, Arayat, Pampanga, is within **National Park Sub-Zone (NP-SZ)** as per General Zoning Ordinance No. 28 series of 2017 of the Sangguniang Bayan of Municipality of Arayat and ratified under SP Resolution No. 4809 Series September 15, 2017 at the Provincial Capitol Province of Pampanga.

TCT NO./Tax Dec. No	Area (sq.m.)	Location
TCT No. 343369-R / GR2020-02-0024-00752	73,964	San Juan Baño, Arayat, Pampanga
TOTAL AREA	73,964 sq.m.	

This Certification is being issued upon request of the interested party for these purposes only.

Given this 30th day of September 2024, at Arayat, Pampanga.

Prepared By:

NATHANIEL A. SISON
MPDC Staff

Approved By:

Eng. ENRIQUE R. OCAMPO
MPDC Zoning Officer

MASISLANG ARAYAT

Figure 2.3.19 Zoning Certificate. Retrieved from Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

COMPREHENSIVE LAND USE PLANNING (CLUPS)

EXISTING LAND USE MAP

The land use of the existing Mt. Arayat National Park Resort is under the parks and recreation zone of Arayat.

Figure 2.3.20 Land Use Map. Courtesy of Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

ELEVATION MAP

The site is slightly elevated as its barangay where it is located has a higher level of elevation compared to others

Figure 2.3.21 Elevation Map. Courtesy of Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

SLOPE MAP

The site configuration and topography are flat to hilly because it is located at the skirt near the foot of Mt. Arayat

Figure 2.3.22 Slope Map. Courtesy of Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

RIVER MAP

The closest river to the site is the Pampanga River located at east boundary of San Juan Bano Arayat Pampanga.

Figure 2.3.23 River Map. Courtesy of Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

FLOOD HAZARD MAP

The project site has low prone category for flood hazard

Figure 2.3.24 Flood Hazard Map. Courtesy of Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

LANDSLIDE VULNERABILITY MAP

The site has a low to moderate vulnerability for landslide

Figure 2.3.25 Landslide Vulnerability Map. Courtesy of Office of the Municipal Planning and Development Coordinator of Arayat

CHAPTER 3

DATA ANALYSIS

PRESENTATION OF GATHERED DATA

ARCHITECTURAL PROGRAMMING

EXISTING LAWS AND STANDARDS

3.1 PRESENTATION OF GATHERED DATA

3.1.1 Survey Results

The survey was aimed to collect data to determine the underlying opinions, preference, and behavior of the probable user. It is distributed to the people inside and outside Arayat and received the response of 109 individual.

A. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Figure 3.1.1 Survey Demographic: Age and Employment

AGE RANGE (AGE)	EMPLOYMENT					Grand Total
	Employed	Retiree	Self Employed	Student	Unemployed	
18 - 25 years old	40	4	1	2	9	56
26 - 40 years old	19	0	4	1	8	32
41 - 59 years old	11	0	1	3	4	19
60 and above	0	0	1	1	0	2
Grand Total	34	3	10	41	21	109

Table 3.1.1 Survey Demographic: Age and Employment Status

Figures (3.1.1) and Table (3.1.1) reveal that most respondents are aged 18-25 years old (51.4%) which status were mostly Student. It was followed by the age bracket of 26-40 years old (29.4 %) which status mostly fall under employed. The rest of the respondents are aged 41- 59 years old (17.4%) and 60 above.

Figure 3.1.2 Survey Demographic: Gender

<i>Gender (Kasarian):</i>	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
Female	62.39%	68
Male	36.70%	40
Prefer not to say	0.92%	1
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.2 Survey Demographic: Gender

The survey determined that most of the respondents are female with a total of 68 responses (62.39%) and male with a total of 40 responses (36.70%). Some 0.92% (1) prefer not to say.

Figure 3.1.3 Survey Demographic: Municipality

<i>Municipality</i>	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
Apalit	5.50%	6
Arayat	43.12%	47
Bacolor	0.92%	1
Candaba	0.92%	1
Lubao	2.75%	3
Macabebe	0.92%	1
Magalang	0.92%	1
Mexico	4.59%	5
Minalin	1.83%	2
Outside Pampanga	18.35%	20
Porac	0.92%	1
San Fernando	4.59%	5
San Luis	3.67%	4
San Simon	0.92%	1
Santa Rita	0.92%	1
Santo Tomas	0.92%	1
Sta. Ana	8.26%	9
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.3 Survey Demographic: Municipality

The survey result shows that predominantly of the participants are from Arayat which is also the location of the proposed redevelopment. It exhibits 43.12% of the total number of participants which amount to 47 individuals from the municipality. The next highest number of participants were from outside of Pampanga which are individuals that were also situated near the province. The rest are from other municipality such as Sta. Ana, Apalit, Mexico, San Fernando, Lubao, Minalin and other Municipalities of Pampanga (See Table 3.1.3)

B. PERSONAL KNOWLEDGE ABOUT WELLNESS AND RECREATION

Figure 3.1.4 Survey Wellness and Recreation

RESPONSE	COUNT	PERCENTRAGE
No	13	11.93%
Yes	96	88.07%
Grand Total	109	100.00%

Table 3.1.4 Survey Wellness and Recreation

96 responded that they know wellness and recreation center and 13 responded that they are not familiar and does not know Wellness and Recreation Center.

Figure 3.1.5 Survey Wellness and Recreation Around Arayat

RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
No	40.37%	44
Yes	59.63%	65
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.5 Survey Wellness and Recreation Around Arayat

Majority of the participants, 59.63% or 65 individuals are aware of wellness and recreation centers in Arayat while the rest with 40.37% equivalent of 44 individuals responded the opposite regarding wellness and recreation center in Arayat.

Figure 3.1.6 Survey Wellness and Recreation Around Arayat

RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
No	21.10%	23
Yes	78.90%	86
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.6 Survey Wellness and Recreation Around Arayat

Seventy-eight percent (78.90%) responded that they already visited in a wellness or recreation center. On the other hand, twenty-one percent (21.10%) answered that they still not visited wellness or recreation center.

Figure 3.1.7 Survey Outside or Inside Arayat

RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
Inside Arayat (loob)	34.86%	38
Never Been	21.10%	23
Outside Arayat (labas)	44.04%	48
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.7 Survey Outside or Inside Arayat

RESPONSE	INSIDE OR OUTSIDE ARAYAT		Grand Total
	Inside Arayat (loob)	Outside Arayat (labas)	
Yes	38	45	83
Grand Total	38	45	83

Table 3.1.8 Survey Outside or Inside Arayat

In the eighty-six (86) people that responded “yes” and visited wellness or recreation center (Table 3.1.6), the survey showed that 38 (people) of them visited inside Arayat while 45 (people) gone to wellness or recreation center outside Arayat.

Figure 3.1.8 Survey Facilities

In this Figure (Figure 3.1.8) it determined what recreation and wellness facilities that most of the people visited. Resort and Park/ Nature Park are the places where most of the people visit for recreation (79.8 %). It is followed by sports center (33%), spa (31.2%) for wellness, and other facilities (see Figure 3.1.8).

Figure 3.1.9 Survey Frequency of Visit

RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
Frequent (Madalas)	8.26%	9
Occasionally (Minsan)	61.47%	67
Rarely (Bihira)	30.28%	33
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.9 Survey Frequency of Visit

Figure 3.1.10 Survey Arayat National Park

As the goal of the survey is to determine the preferences and opinions of people for the development of the project, the participants are divided into two which are those who visited the Arayat National Park and those who does not yet visited. In this figure (Figure 3.1.10) the responses are 53.2 % or 58 people who visited the existing project and the rest with 46.8% or 51 people who haven't yet visited the project.

RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
No	46.79%	51
Yes	53.21%	58
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.10 Survey Arayat National Park

Municipality	Have you visited the Mt. Arayat National Park ?		
Municipality / Ad	No	Yes	Grand Total
Apalit	6		6
Arayat	6	41	47
Bacolor	1		1
Candaba		1	1
Lubao	3		3
Macabebe	1		1
Magalang	1		1
Mexico	4	1	5
Minalin	2		2
Outside Pampanga	15	5	20
Porac		1	1
San Fernando	5		5
San Luis		4	4
San Simon		1	1
Santa Rita	1		1
Santo Tomas	1		1
Sta. Ana	5	4	9
Grand Total	51	58	109

Table 3.1.11 Survey Arayat National Park

Figure 3.1.11 Survey Arayat National Park

From the previous survey (Table 3.1.10), 58 people already visited Arayat National Park. Among these number the 41 people who visited are from municipality of Arayat where the project is situated. The other people who visited came from other municipalities such as San Luis (4), Sta. Ana (4), Candaba(1), Mexico (1), Porac(1), San Simon (1), and even outside Pampanga (5). g

Summary For Personal Knowledge of Wellness and Recreation

To summarize, based on the number of participants who took part in the study most enjoy visiting wellness or recreation centers and know several facilities that offer the service. Among the different wellness and recreation facilities, majority of the people go to several resorts and nature parks and some at sports center and spa. It also showed in the surveys that in those facilities that people visited almost equal in number gone to centers situated outside and inside Arayat. Most of the participants by ratio of 40 to 60 – who 60% of them, are familiar of wellness and recreation center in Arayat. While for Arayat National Park, half of the participants visited the resort and they are from the different municipality of Pampanga.

C. PERSONAL EXPERIENCE IN ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK

In rating 1-5, With 5 being the highest. Rate your experience about the existing areas/ aspect of the Arayat National Park

Figure 3.1.12 Survey: Pool Ratings

The survey revealed that in rate of one to five (1-5) as five (5) being the highest. Most of participants rated the swimming pools as 4 (33.3%), 3 (29.3%), Ratings-5 (24%), 1 and 2 (6.7%). This shows that most of the people enjoys the current pool setup and experience.

Figure 3.1.13 Survey: Utility Ratings

The survey revealed that in rate of one to five (1-5) as five (5) being the highest. Most of participants rated the utilities as 3 (28%), 4 (20%), 5 (18.7%), 2 (17.3%) and 1 (16%). This Shows that the utilities are on average level of rating.

Figure 3.1.14 Survey: Cottages Ratings

The survey revealed that in rate of one to five (1-5) as five (5) being the highest. Most of participants rated the cottages as Ratings- 3 (33.3%), Ratings- 5 (26.7%), Ratings-4 (21.3%), Ratings-1 (10.7%) and Ratings-2 (8%).

Figure 3.1.15 Survey: Villas Ratings

The survey revealed that in rate of one to five (1-5) as five (5) being the highest. Most of participants rated the villas as 4 (28%), 3 (24%), 1 (18.7%), 5 (16%) and 2 (13.3%).

Figure 3.1.16 Survey: Event Center Ratings

The survey revealed that in rate of one to five (1-5) as five (5) being the highest. Most of participants rated the event center as 4 (30.7%), 5 (26.7%), 3 (21.3%), 1 and 2 (10.7%).

Figure 3.1.17 Survey: Food Stalls Ratings

The survey revealed that in rate of one to five (1-5) as five (5) being the highest. Most of participants rated the Food Stalls as 3 (29.3%), 5 (25.3%), 4 (24%), 1 (12%), and 2 (9.3%).

Figure 3.1.18 Survey: Parking and Transportation Ratings

The survey revealed that in rate of one to five (1-5) as five (5) being the highest. Most of participants rated the parking and transportation as 5 (37.3%), 4 (29.3%), 3 (21.3%), 1 (9.3%), and 2 (2.7%).

Figure 3.1.19 Survey: Other Attraction Ratings

The survey revealed that in rate of one to five (1-5) as five (5) being the highest. Most of participants rated the other attraction as 4 (34.7%), 5 (29.3%), 3 (24%), 1 (8%) and 2 (4%).

Figure 3.1.20 Survey: Experience

What do you think the areas/aspect that are needed of improvement?

Cleanliness (15 Responses)

Majority of the participants responded that the issues they wanted to focus on is the cleanliness of the site with 15 related answers about sanitation and site management for cleanliness. The participants pointed out concerns on garbage disposal and neatness of every corner of the site. The participants specified spaces such as pools, cottages, food stalls, comfort rooms, and other spots that need cleanliness.

Cleanliness (Personal Responses)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• As for the pools, don't let dirt get inside the pools• Cleanliness of the National Park• Cleanliness• Cleanliness of the area• Cleanliness of the food by using nets over the pools• Cleanliness, Sanitation, Comfort Room,• Cleanliness of Pool, Cottage, Food Stall• Cleanliness.• Kalinisan• Maintaining the cleanliness of the area to preserve the natural resources.• Panatiling malinis ang mga swimming pool• Sanitation• Waste Management around the Mt. Arayat National Park• We noticed that there are frogs and other unsanitary garbages while the pools are being filled. It would be more appropriate if they appropriately clean the pools and the surroundings. The ambiance also doesn't feel welcoming with the structure and paints.• Yung dapat siguro kailangan paunladin yung to aware people that bawal mag tapon ng mga basura kahit saan.

Table 3.1.12 Survey: Cleanliness Concerns

Overall Facilities (9 Responses)

Aside from cleanliness there are nine (9) responses that are related to overall improvement of facilities. The participants mentioned the need of renovation of different structures that are erected including their overall design.

Overall Facilities (Personal Responses)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• All spaces have room for improvement.• Design of Structures• Facilities• Facilities and utilities• Madami kailangang ayusin tulad ng mga retail store maayos na mga paliguan changing rooms, malinis na toilets at swimming pools, tamang parking area• Marami• Renovation like add more pools and villas.• Sometimes people do want the ambiance of the facility itself, but some other parks don't have that necessary ambiance that most of the people like. So, as for me it is the ambiance.• Structures and ambiance

Table 3.1.13 Survey: Overall Facilities

Environmental and Sustainable (9 Responses)

Environmental concerns and sustainability also revealed in the responses of the participants. Nine (9) related answer brought up suggestions about proper landscaping and greenery that may aid the beautification of the project. It is also revealed that facilities should adhere to green architecture, therefore it will not cause adverse effect to the environment.

Environmental and Sustainable (Personal Responses)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Facilities and activities that can attract tourists and promote the place and environment• Facilities and their function as well a enhancement of landscape design

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilities without sacrificing the nature • Keep the areas to be greenery cz it's an attraction to the foreign people • More on view gardens for relaxation • Pag papalago sa likas na kalikasan • Preserving the natural environment and maintaining its cleanliness. • Pag iingat at kakinisan Ng ating bundok • Oo, sa pamamagitan ng pagtatanim ng mga halamanna sa national park, lumakas nag tourist destination
--

Table 3.1.14 Survey: Environmental and Sustainable

New Spaces (8 Responses)

Other participants (8) suggested that proposing other activities and spaces will help the project to improve more. Including to these are additional attraction and recreational spaces that the tourist will enjoy. They also mention Food, Bike trails and Garden.

New Spaces (Personal Responses)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bike trail • Diverse Interactive Areas • Food variety • I think the areas that need to improve are the ways in how they present the food, the proper waste disposal, and service. • Place Attractions • Recreational spaces for the all • Top of hundred step should have a rest area and good ambiance to see like flowers and garden. • Tree house

Table 3.1.15 Survey: Space Suggestion

Toilets, Utilities and Cottages (7 Responses)

Utilities such as toilets, showers and changing rooms also showed in the survey as a subject for improvement. Several concerns shows that these spaces are not easily accessible to people. Cottages are also mentioned alongside with utilities as they are far from other spaces.

Toilets, Utilities and Cottages (Personal Responses)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of toilets and shower to pools • Cottages and the swimming pools • Cottages and Utilities • Pool and toilets • Pools and toilets • Service, utilities and swimming pools. • Utilities (Shower and Toilet)

Table 3.1.16 Survey: Utilities

Organization (7 Responses)

Organization related answers are specified in the response of seven (7) participants. This organization pertains to both management and the different spaces of the site. Including to the organization of spaces are the path walks and different structures of the project.

Organization (Personal Responses)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be organized and accommodating • Limitation of the crowd • Parking • pathways, pools (more pools i think, last time i went pools are full • Transportation • Transportation and accessibility • Openness

Table 3.1.17 Survey: Organization

Safety and Security (3 Responses)

The survey showed 3 related answers pertaining to Safety and security of the site and different structures built inside the project

Safety and Security (Personal Responses)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve safety protocols especially for the kids. • It's accessibility and safeness of the area. • The security should be more strength

Table 3.1.18 Survey: Safety and Security

Figure 3.1.21 Survey: Activities

D. SPACE SUGGESTIONS

Figure 3.1.22 Survey: Interests

Figure 3.1.23 Survey: Specific Spaces that are Looking For

In seeking a wellness and recreation center a big portion in deciding factor where would the participants visit is the ambiance of the place. It was followed by the services and facilities offered by a certain place or destination. Other considerations that are selected by the participants are food, location, design of structure, transportation and villas was shown respectively that also have an importance for their choice.

In work with the different consideration mentioned, specific spaces and facilities are also given high regards by the participants of the study. Including to these specific spaces are food park, café and resto, parks and playground, activity and interactive area and relaxation area. Other spaces that have regards are spa and wellness, villas and cottages, sports and jogging area.

E. FAVORABILITY

What do you think is the relevance of building wellness and recreation that are also sustainable and close to environment?

Relaxation and Health (51 Responses)

In one hundred and one (101) responses from participants, 51 are related to health and relaxation. Large number of participants believed that building wellness and recreation center near natural environment and nature will elevates one's health. As the location is close to greeneries it is suitable for the purpose of achieving health and wellness. Participants mentioned that facilities or buildings close to nature tend to be more calming and relaxing as it also has less pollution and noise from the busy world. Participants also pointed out that wellness and recreation center help to promote positive behavior, relieve stress and uplift the overall mental and physical well-being of the people.

Sustainable and Environmental (31 responses)

In one hundred and one (101) responses from participants, 31 were related to the sustainability of the project. Most of the responses that came from the participants indicated the importance of sustainability to the project. They specified that building wellness and recreation center that is sustainable is vital in today's issue of climate change as it covers the goal of a wellness center with still regards to the condition of the of the environment. Sustainable structures positively influence the overall ecosystem from conserving water, minimizing pollutants and lowering the carbon footprint of the site. These considerations will help not only the management of the site but also positively influence the end user of the project.

Tourism (19 responses)

In one hundred and one (101) responses from participants, 19 answer were related to the tourism aspect of the municipality. Participants have high anticipation that redeveloping the site and building a wellness and recreation center will move towards improvement of Arayat tourism. Creating a wellness and recreation center will give people a place to go, a destination that can be a tourist attraction not only in Arayat but in all municipality of Pampanga. This will not only provide fun and wellness, but it will also improve the economy of the municipality.

Figure 3.1.24 Survey: People's Perception About the Project

A	B	C
RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
No	1.83%	2
Yes	98.17%	107
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.19 Survey: People's Perception About the Project

Figure 3.1.25 Survey: Peoples Favorability

RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE	COUNT
Approved (Sang-Ayon)	31.19%	34
Not Approved (Hindi Sang-Ayon)	1.83%	2
Somehow Approved (Kahit Papaano ay Sang-Ayon)	3.67%	4
Strongly Approved (Malakas na Sumasang-Ayon)	63.30%	69
Grand Total	100.00%	109

Table 3.1.20 Survey: Peoples Favorability

Participants positively responded to the proposal of redevelopment of Arayat National Park with a 63.30 % (69 responses) of Strongly agree individuals and a 31.19% (34 responses) of approved individuals. On the other hand, a small portion of somehow approved with 3.67% (4 Responses) and 1.83% (2 Responses) of not approved participants. Overall, the favorability of the project has a high support to the people for it to be redevelop.

3.1.2 Interview

Primary Data Mt. Arayat National Park (Arayat National Park Management)

These data are based on conducted interview with the management within Mt. Arayat National Park

Arayat National Park Operating Hours

Monday: 8 AM- 5 PM

Tuesday: 8 AM- 5PM

Wednesday: 8AM – 5PM

Thursday: 8AM- 5PM

Friday: 8AM – 5PM

Saturday: 8AM- 5PM

Sunday 8AM -5PM

How many people visits the resort in everyday basis?

Headcount of the people who visit the site differ each day and each season. Sometimes or some days, the site are flooded by visitors and sometimes there are not much foot traffic inside the project. During regular days (regular season) the average of people who visit the Arayat National Park are around 50-100 people which are mostly site seeing and training in the area. During summer (peak season), around 400-500 people each day come to visit and experience the resort.

What is the peak season of the resort? How did you manage people?

(How long does people stay in the resort?)

Peak season of Arayat National Park are during summer season from March to May with an average of 400 visitors each day. Most of the people stay whole day (6-7 hours) in cottages and swimming pools that the MANP offer. In spite of numbers of people, cottages and open spaces within the park suffice to the demand of the people of the visitors in the resort. There are also other areas where people can entertain people aside from pools such as playground, 100 steps attraction, fishpond and the greeneries of the site.

PEAK MONTHS OF MT. ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK

TOURIST ARRIVAL OF MT. ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK 2018			
MONTHS	VISITOR (PAID ENTRANCE)	VISITOR (FREE ENTRANCE)	REMARKS
JANUARY	309	51	
FEBRUARY	1,178	112	
MARCH	3,613	130	
APRIL	5,487	119	
MAY	4,303	102	
JUNE	481	96	
JULY			RAINY SEASON
AUGUST			RAINY SEASON
SEPTEMBER		66	RAINY SEASON
OCTOBER	76	12	
NOVEMBER	176	23	
DECEMBER	54	14	
TOTAL	15,677	695	16,372

Table 3.1.2.(1) Tourist Arrival of Mt. Arayat

Source: Office of the Municipal Tourism, 2022

What are the people looking for when they visit the Mt. Arayat National Park Resort?

Arayat National Park is known for its freshwater pools (cold water) that came from the mountains. People go in Arayat National Park for swimming and experience the waterfalls of the resort. Residents of Arayat and returnees from other province come back for the pools and the close to nature environment of the site. First timers ask for other spaces like cottages, resto, food courts, and other service that they can avail in the site.

What are the difficulties in managing the site? Are there specific problems you encountered?

Managing the people (visitors) is one of the most challenging parts of managing the resort. Some people neglect the safety rules and practice inside the project specially in the pool areas that may cause them injury. Other problem includes proper waste disposal because people tend to throw their waste on grounds and every corner of the site.

In numbers of visitor that visit the site during peak season problem also emerged in monitoring because pool was also became crowded of people that is hard to observe everyone.

What do you think the areas needed of improvement?

The Mt. Arayat National Park was still in the process of improvement and development. Redevelopment of the project should focus on maximizing the lot for the development and put importance to the different utilities and lodgings in the resort which are currently the disadvantage and needed improvement in all spaces of the project.

Do you think the redevelopment of Mt. Arayat National Park Resort into a wellness and recreation area can help to attract more visitors outside and inside Pampanga? Why?

Yes. Arayat National Park is one of the known attractions in Arayat and known as the face of Arayat in terms of natural resorts. Development and improvements will bring additional appeal to the resort.

**Secondary Data Review (Bansi, C., Evangelista K.A, Venzon C.R (2023).
Balikhaan: Mt. Arayat Park Reimagined)**

What are the possible activities that are applicable for the project like the wellness and recreation center in Arayat National Park?

Activities with less disturbance to natural setting of the environment. To promote serenity and maintain peace in atmosphere of the park it is advised to consider activities that will not generate excessive noise pollution. Activities such team building, social gathering, wellness and recreation, trekking, camping, ziplining, sports program and other similar activities may operate with consideration to noise.

What theme should the park follow?

Just like other lands and projects under Nipas Act of 2018, the park should follow sustainable development theme and nature related design. MANP (Mt. Arayat National Park) as an area rich with natural resources and material the ideal concept is to utilized the existing environment for its future use.

Is it allowed to relocate trees within the site?

Relocation and cutting off trees are in jurisdiction of the Regional Executive Director of DENR for this kind of project. Trees that are to be relocated and cut must be apply for request and permit under the extension of Tree Cutting and Earth Balling Permits for naturally grown trees in regional office except cutting for public purposes

of National Government Agencies which includes the DPWH, DOTr, DepEd, DA, DOH, CHED, DOE, and NIA pursuant to DAO no. 2020-06 which can be issued by Community Environment and National Resources.

Is the project site of Mt. Arayat National Park open for expansion?

Mt. Arayat National Park is a 3,715-hectares in Area. Currently, it has an existing 7-hectares resort that was subjected to the five-year Comprehensive Development Management plan of 14-hectares Resort as from 2018-2023 which will house lodgings, tourism amenities and different supporting structures. Expansion is possible through application of Environmental Compliance certificate (ECC) proving that the proposed project will not cause significant negative impact to the natural environment.

3.1.3 TOURIST ARRIVALS

Below are the different tourist destination and Recreation areas in Arayat with their visitor count in specific years starting from 2017

ARAYAT 2017 TOURIST ARRIVALS	
RECREATIONAL	VISITORS PER ANNUM
1. CHINGU HIDDEN PARADISE	2,924
2. VILLA ARVA RESORT	360
3. GINTUNG PAKPAK	198
4. BALITI DAM	145
5. MT. ARAYAT HONESTY AND RECREATIONAL FARM	178
6. NINGS RESORT	3,070
7. VILLA JUMERA	850
8. MICS PARDISE RESORT	15,954
9. CESARES RESORT	7,250
10. VILLA ARIZONA RESORT	4,500
11. FUNVILLE RESORT	1,985
12. TREE HOUSE	45
13. MAJIC JADE RESORT	6,244
OVERALL TOTAL= 43,703	

Table 3.1.3. (1).Arayat 2017 Tourist Arrivals Source: Office of Municipal Tourism,2022

MT. ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK TOURIST ARRIVAL 2017

TOURIST ARRIVAL OF MT. ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK 2017			
MONTHS	VISITOR (PAID ENTRANCE)	VISITOR (FREE ENTRANCE)	REMARKS
JANUARY	258	45	
FEBRUARY	988	98	
MARCH	3,433	123	
APRIL	5,244	143	
MAY	3,865	95	
JUNE	378	83	
JULY			RAINY SEASON
AUGUST			RAINY SEASON
SEPTEMBER		34	RAINY SEASON
OCTOBER	47	10	
NOVEMBER	144	22	
DECEMBER	25	12	
TOTAL	14,382	665	15,047

Table 3.1.3. (2). Mt. Arayat National Park 2017 Tourist Arrivals

Source: Office of the Municipal Tourism, 2022

ARAYAT TOURIST ARRIVALS 2018

ARAYAT 2018 TOURIST ARRIVALS	
RECREATIONAL	VISITORS PER ANNUM
1. CHINGU HIDDEN PARADISE	72,761
2. VILLA ARVA RESORT	1,171
3. GINTUNG PAKPAK	249
4. BALITI DAM	184
5. MT. ARAYAT HONESTY AND RECREATIONAL FARM	266
6. NINGS RESORT	4,370
7. VILLA JUMERA	1,286
8. MICS PARDISE RESORT	27,220
9. CESARES RESORT	10,064
10. VILLA ARIZONA RESORT	5,780
11. FUNVILLE RESORT	2,437
12. TREE HOUSE	100
13. MAJIC JADE RESORT	12,334
OVERALL TOTAL= 141,655	

Table 3.1.3. (3). Arayat 2018 Tourist Arrivals

Source: Office of Municipal Tourism, 2022

MT. ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK TOURIST ARRIVAL 2018

TOURIST ARRIVAL OF MT. ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK 2018			
MONTHS	VISITOR (PAID ENTRANCE)	VISITOR (FREE ENTRANCE)	REMARKS
JANUARY	309	51	
FEBRUARY	1,178	112	
MARCH	3,613	130	
APRIL	5,487	119	
MAY	4,303	102	
JUNE	481	96	
JULY			RAINY SEASON
AUGUST			RAINY SEASON
SEPTEMBER		66	RAINY SEASON
OCTOBER	76	12	
NOVEMBER	176	23	
DECEMBER	54	14	
TOTAL	15,677	695	16,372

Table 3.1.3. (4). Mt. Arayat National Park 2018 Tourist Arrivals

Source: Office of the municipal Tourism, 2022

ARAYAT TOURIST ARRIVALS 2019

ARAYAT 2019 TOURIST ARRIVALS	
RECREATIONAL	VISITORS PER ANNUM
1. CHINGU HIDDEN PARADISE	10,666
2. VILLA ARVA RESORT	1,235
3. GINTUNG PAKPAK	342
4. BALITI DAM	143
5. MT. ARAYAT HONESTY AND RECREATIONAL FARM	158
6. NINGS RESORT	4,138
7. VILLA JUMERA	16,835
8. MICS PARDISE RESORT	20,646
9. CESARES RESORT	6,234
10. VILLA ARIZONA RESORT	5,524
11. FUNVILLE RESORT	6,340
12. TREE HOUSE	105
13. MAJIC JADE RESORT	18,427
OVERALL TOTAL= 90,793	

Table 3.1.3. (5). Arayat 2019 Tourist Arrivals

Source: Office of Municipal Tourism, 2022

MT. ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK TOURIST ARRIVAL 2019

TOURIST ARRIVAL OF MT. ARAYAT NATIONAL PARK 2019			
MONTHS	VISITOR (PAID ENTRANCE)	VISITOR (FREE ENTRANCE)	REMARKS
JANUARY	786	36	
FEBRUARY	596	23	
MARCH	1,466	86	
APRIL	4,369	62	
MAY	3,224	104	
JUNE	1,041	70	
JULY			RAINY SEASON
AUGUST			RAINY SEASON
SEPTEMBER	185	11	
OCTOBER	298	16	
NOVEMBER	486	78	
DECEMBER	750	76	
TOTAL	13,201	562	13,763

Table 3.1.3. (6). Mt. Arayat National Park 2019 Tourist Arrivals

Source: Office of the municipal Tourism, 2022

3.2 ARCHITECTURAL PROGRAMMING

ARCHITECTURAL PROGRAMMING											
ARCHITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:	MAIN ADMINISTRATIVE BUILDING (ASLAGAN BUILDING)										
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s	Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal	
					Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture		
LOBBY AND WAITING AREA	15	STAFF	0.98	14.7	1	30	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	7.5	22.20
	30	VISITORS	0.98	29.4		6	SOFA SET	2	1	12	41.40
			0.98	0		4	TABLE	1.2	0.6	2.88	2.88
			0.98	0		1	BILLIARD TABLE	2.36	1.37	3.2332	3.23
			0.98	0		1	BAR TABLE	3	1.5	4.5	4.50
ADMIN OFFICE	1	ADMIN	0.98	0.98	1	1	ADMIN TABLE	1.2	0.8	0.96	1.94
	5	VISITORS	0.98	4.9		1	TABLE	1.2	0.6	0.72	5.62
	1	STAFF	0.98	0.98		2	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.48
			0.98	0		1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	2.00
			0.98	0		1	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.30
			0.98	0		1	KITCHEN SINK	2	0.7	1.4	1.40
			0.98	0		1	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	1.4	1.40
			0.98	0		1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	0.24
ENTERTAINMENT AREA	20	VISTORS	0.98	19.6	1	2	BILLARD TABLE	2.36	1.37	6.4664	26.07
INFORMATION DESK AND RECEPTION	2	STAFF	0.98	1.96	1	1	COUNTER	3	0.7	2.1	4.06
MINI BAR COUNTER	3	STAFF	0.98	2.94	1	1	COUNTER	3	0.7	2.1	5.04
			0.98	0		20	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	5	5.00
						2	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
PUBLIC TOILET	14	VISITORS	0.98	27.44	2	20	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	4.8	32.24
			0.98	0		10	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	3	3.00
EMPLOYEES LOUNGE	15	EMPLOYEES	0.98	14.7	1	1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	16.70

			0.98	0		1	WATERCLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	0.24
			0.98	0		1	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.30
			0.98	0		1	LOCKERS	2	0.6	1.2	1.20
			0.98	0		2	TABLE	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
			0.98	0		3	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	2.16	2.16
			0.98	0		1	COUNTER	1.2	0.7	0.84	0.84
OFFICE AREA	15	EMPLOYEES	0.98	14.7	1	15	TABLE	1.2	0.6	10.8	25.50
			0.98	0		20	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	5	5.00
			0.98	0		5	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	3.6	3.60
			0.98	0		1	PANTRY	3	2	6	6.00
			0.98	0		3	EQUIPMENTS	1	1	3	3.00
CONFERENCE ROOMS	20	EMPLOYEES	0.98	19.6	1	20	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	5	24.60
			0.98	0		2	TABLE	2	1.2	4.8	4.80
			0.98	0		1	TECHBOOTH	2	2	4	4.00
CENTRAL SECURITY	2	EMPLOYEES	0.98	1.96	1	1	TABLE	1.2	0.6	0.72	2.68
	5	VISITORS	0.98	4.9		5	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	1.25	6.15
UTILITY ROOM			0.98	0						0	0.00
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
CISTERN	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	WATER TANKS	2	2	4	8.90
A.H.U ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	AIR CONDITIONING UNITS	4	6	24	28.90
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
			0.98	0		2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
ELEVATOR LOBBY	20	VISITOR	0.98	19.6	1	2	ELEVATOR	1.8	2.1	7.56	27.16
STORAGE ROOMS	15	EMPLOYEES	0.98	14.7	2	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	16.14
										Net Floor Area	374.77
										Total Net Floor Area	374.77
	Circulation:	40%		TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:		524.6774				TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:	699.57
				TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:		713.5613				TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)	713.56

Table 3.2.1 Architecture Programming of Main Administrative Building

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:		INTERACTIVE GALLERY AND RESTO (ALAYA BUILDING)									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s		Area needed	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal
						Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment,	Length	Width	Total area	
LOBBY AND RECEPTION	10	STAFF	0.98	9.8	1	20	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	5	14.80
	70	VISITORS	0.98	68.6		10	SOFA SET	2	1	20	88.60
			0.98	0		5	TABLE	1.2	0.6	3.6	3.60
			0.98	0		1	INFORMATION TABLE	3	1.5	4.5	4.50
INTERACTIVE GALLERY	70	VISITORS	0.98	68.6	1	20	TABLE	1.2	0.6	14.4	83.00
			0.98	0		20	OTHER AFTIFACTS	2	1	40	40.00
			0.98	0		20	SHELVES	2	0.6	24	24.00
CURATOR OFFICE	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9		2	TABLE	1.2	0.8	1.92	6.82
STORAGE	10	EMPLOYEES	0.98	9.8		5	TABLE	1.2	0.8	4.8	14.60
			0.98	0		10	SHELVES	2	1	20	20.00
LIBRARY AND ARCHIVES	3	EMPLOYEES	0.98	2.94	1	15	TABLES	1.2	0.6	10.8	13.74
	20	VISITORS	0.98	19.6		10	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	2.5	22.10
			0.98	0		6	SOFA SET	2	1	12	12.00
			0.98	0		1	INFORMATION TABLE	2	0.6	1.2	1.20
			0.98	0		10	BOOK SHELVES	2	1	20	20.00
ADMIN OFFICE	1	MANAGER	0.98	0.98	1	2	TABLE	1.2	0.8	1.92	2.90
	5	VISTORS	0.98	4.9		2	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	0.5	5.40
			0.98	0		1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	2.00
			0.98	0		1	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	1.4	1.40
			0.98	0		1	KITCHEN SINK	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.30
PUBLIC TOILET	14	VISITORS	0.98	13.72	1	14	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	3.36	17.08
				0		12	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	3.6	3.60
RESTO (2ND FLOOR)	10	EMPLOYEES	0.98	9.8	1	30	TABLE	1.2	1.2	43.2	53.00
	40	VISITORS	0.98	39.2		50	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	12.5	51.70
			0.98	0		1	COUNTER	6	0.6	3.6	3.60
KITCHEN (RESTO)	10	EMPLOYEES	0.98	9.8	1	2	AISLE TABLE	4	1	8	17.80
			0.98	0		6	RACKS	1.2	0.6	4.32	4.32

			0.98	0		2	RANGE	0.75	0.65	0.975	0.98
			0.98	0		2	DISHWASHING SINK	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
STORAGE(RESTO)	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	2	4	SHELVES	2	1	8	12.90
ALFRESCO	30	VISITORS	0.98	29.4	1	10	TABLES	1.2	1.2	14.4	43.80
			0.98	0		30	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	7.5	7.50
PUBLIC TOILET	14	VISITORS	0.98	13.72	1	14	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	3.36	17.08
			0.98	0		12	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	3.6	3.60
WASH AREA	4	VISITORS	0.98	3.92		4	SINK	0.5	0.5	1	4.92
EMPLOYEES LOUNGE	20	EMPLOYEES	0.98	19.6	2	2	SOFA SET	2	1	4	23.60
			0.98	0		2	TABLE	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
			0.98	0		2	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.48	0.48
			0.98	0		2	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.60
			0.98	0		2	KITCHEN SINK	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.60
			0.98	0		2	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	2.8	2.80
CHEFS OFFICE	1	CHEF	0.98	0.98	1	2	TABLE	1.2	0.8	1.92	2.90
	5	VISTORS	0.98	4.9		2	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	0.5	5.40
			0.98	0		1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	2.00
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
CISTERN	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	WATER TANKS	2	2	4	8.90
A.H.U ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	AIR CONDITIONING UNITS	4	6	48	52.90
STP	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	4	SEGREGATION CHAMBERS	5	2.5	50	54.90
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
			0.98	0		2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
ELEVATOR LOBBY	10	VISITOR	0.98	9.8	1	2	ELEVATOR	1.8	2.1	7.56	17.36
SECURITY OFFICE	2	EMPLOYEES	0.98	1.96	1	1	TABLE	1.2	0.6	0.72	2.68
	5	VISITORS	0.98	4.9		5	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	1.25	6.15
Total Net Floor Area											827.01
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				1157.807	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				1543.74
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:						1574.618	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				1574.62

Table 3.2.2 Architecture Programming of Interactive Gallery and Resto

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY

NAME OF AREA:		DENR (MENR) OFFICE BUILDING									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s		Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal
						Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture	
LOBBY AND WAITING AREA	5	STAFF	0.98	4.9	1	5	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	1.25	6.15
	10	VISITORS	0.98	9.8		1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	11.80
			0.98	0		1	TABLE	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72
INFORMATION AND RECEPTION	2	STAFF	0.98	1.96	1	1	COUNTER	2	0.7	1.4	3.36
KITCHEN	7	EMPLOYEES	0.98	6.86	1	3	CABINETS	1.2	0.6	2.16	9.02
			0.98	0		2	SINK	1	0.5	1	1.00
			0.98	0		2	RANGE	0.75	0.65	0.975	0.98
			0.98	0		7	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	1.75	1.75
			0.98	0		1	TABLE	2	0.8	1.6	1.60
						1	COUNTERTOP	3	0.7	2.1	2.10
MINI LIVING AREA	5	PEOPLE	0.98	4.9	1	1	TABLE	0.8	0.8	0.64	5.54
						1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	2.00
MENRO OFFICE	1	ADMIN	0.98	0.98	1	1	TABLE	1.2	0.8	0.96	1.94
	5	VISITORS	0.98	4.9	1	1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	6.90
			0.98	0	1	2	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.50
			0.98	0	1	2	CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
PUBLIC TOILET	1	VISITORS	0.98	0.98	1	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	1.22
			0.98	0		1	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.30
TOILET AND BATH	1	ADMIN	0.98	0.98	1	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	1.22
						1	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	0.3	0.30
						1	SHOWER	1.2	0.7	0.84	0.84
BEDROOM	2	PEOPLE	0.98	1.96	1	1	BED	2	1.2	2.4	4.36
			0.98	0		2	CABINET	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
CONFERENCE ROOM	15	EMPLOYEES	0.98	14.7	1	15	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	3.75	18.45
			0.98	0		2	TABLE	1.2	0.8	1.92	1.92
			0.98	0		1	CABINET	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72

STORAGE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	4	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	2.88	7.78
Net Floor Area											95.35
Total Net Floor Area											95.35
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:		133.483	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:						177.98
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:				181.5369	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)			181.54			

Table 3.2.3 Architecture Programming of MENRO

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:		SPA AND SAUNA (DALISE BUILDING)									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s		Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal
						Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture	
LOBBY AND WAITING AREA	30	VISITORS	0.98	29.4	1	6	SOFA SET	2	1	12	41.40
	10	STAFF	0.98	9.8	1	30	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	7.5	17.30
			0.98	0		6	TABLE	1.2	0.6	4.32	4.32
COUNTER AND RECEPTION AREA	2	STAFF	0.98	1.96	1	1	COUNTER	2	0.7	1.4	3.36
						4	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	1	1.00
EMPLOYEES LOUNGE	20	EMPLOYEES	0.98	19.6	3	3	SOFA SET	2	1	6	25.60
			0.98	0		2	WATERCLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.48	0.48
			0.98	0		2	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.60
			0.98	0		2	LOCKERS	2	0.6	2.4	2.40
			0.98	0		2	TABLE	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
			0.98	0		1	COUNTER	1.2	0.7	0.84	0.84
			0.98	0		1	COUNTER	1.2	0.7	0.84	0.84
ADMIN OFFICE	1	MANAGER	0.98	0.98	1	2	TABLE	1.2	0.8	1.92	2.90
	5	VISTORS	0.98	4.9		2	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	0.5	5.40
			0.98	0		1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	2.00
			0.98	0		1	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	1.4	1.40
PUBLIC TOILET	10	VISITORS	0.98	9.8	1	10	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	2.4	12.20
				0		10	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	3	3.00
STORAGE	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	6	SHELVES	2	0.6	7.2	12.10
FOOTSPA AREA	10	EMPLOYEES	0.98	9.8	1	20	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	5	14.80

	10	VISITORS	0.98	9.8	1	5	SHELVES	1.2	0.5	3	12.80	
SPA ROOMS HUTS	2	VISITORS	0.98	19.6	10	10	BED	2	0.9	18	37.60	
	2	EMPLOYEES	0.98	1.96		20	SHELVES	1.2	0.5	12	13.96	
SPA ROOMS DELUXE	2	VISITOR	0.98	15.68	8	16	BED	2	0.9	28.8	44.48	
	2	EMPLOYEES	0.98	1.96		32	SHELVES	1.2	0.5	19.2	21.16	
						8	MINI POOL	3	2	48	48.00	
SAUNA HUTS	4	VISITORS	0.98	3.92	4	4	HUTS	3	3	36	39.92	
BAR AND TABLES	20	VISITORS	0.98	19.6	1	1	COUNTER	3	0.7	2.1	21.70	
	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9		20	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	5	9.90	
						5	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	3.6	3.60	
						10	TABLES	1	1	10	10.00	
MINI KITCHEN	5	STAFF	0.98	4.9	1	1	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	1.4	6.30	
			0.98	0		4	TABLE	1.2	0.8	3.84	3.84	
			0.98	0		5	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	1.25	1.25	
			0.98	0		3	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	2.16	2.16	
SHOWER AND LOCKERS	20	VISITORS	0.98	19.6	1	12	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	3.6	23.20	
			0.98	0		20	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	5	5.00	
			0.98	0		6	LOCKER CABINETS	1.2	0.5	3.6	3.60	
			0.98	0		6	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	1.44	1.44	
			0.98	0		20	SHOWER	1.2	0.9	21.6	21.60	
MINI POOL AREA	20	VISITORS	0.98	19.6		1	POOL	8	8	64	83.60	
						7	LOUNGER	2	0.7	9.8	9.80	
UTILITY ROOM											0.00	
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34	
MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34	
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90	
						2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44	
											Net Floor Area	597.47
											Total Net Floor Area	597.47
	Circulation:	40%			TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:	836.458					TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:	1115.28
					TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:	1137.583					TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)	1137.58

Table 3.2.4 Architecture Programming of Spa and Sauna Building

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:		YOGA AND GYM (DALISE BUILDING)									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s		Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal
						Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture	
FITNESS GYM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	6	BENCH	1.2	0.6	4.32	9.22
	25	VISITORS	0.98	24.5		1	INFORMATION DESK	1	0.6	0.6	25.10
			0.98	0		5	THREADMILL	1.58	0.86	6.794	6.79
			0.98	0		4	DUMBEL RACK	1.2	0.4	1.92	1.92
			0.98	0		4	BARBEL RACK	1.2	0.5	2.4	2.40
			0.98	0		4	ADJUSTABLE BENCH	1.2	0.5	2.4	2.40
			0.98	0		5	SHELVES	1.2	0.5	3	3.00
SHOWER AND LOCKERS	25	VISITORS	0.98	24.5	2	10	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	3	27.50
			0.98	0		10	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	2.5	2.50
			0.98	0		6	LOCKER CABINETS	1.2	0.5	3.6	3.60
			0.98	0		4	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.96	0.96
			0.98	0		20	SHOWER	1.2	0.9	21.6	21.60
TOILET	10	VISITORS	0.98	9.8	1	10	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	2.4	12.20
MINI PANTRY	10	VISITOR	0.98	9.8	1	2	SHELVES	1.2	0.5	1.2	11.00
						2	TABLE	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
YOGA STUDIO	5	STAFFS	0.98	4.9	1	10	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	2.5	7.40
	20	VISITORS	0.98	19.6		3	SOFA SET	2	1	6	25.60
						1	YOGA AREA	7	7	49	49.00
SHOWER AND LOCKERS	20	VISITORS	0.98	19.6	2	10	LAVATORY	0.5	0.6	3	22.60
			0.98	0		10	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	2.5	2.50
			0.98	0		3	LOCKER CABINETS	1.2	0.5	1.8	1.80
			0.98	0		4	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.96	0.96
			0.98	0		20	SHOWER	1.2	0.9	21.6	21.60
STORAGE	5	PEOPLE	0.98	4.9	1	2	SHELVES	2	0.6	2.4	7.30
						5	EQUIPMENT AND MATS	1	1	5	5.00
UTILITY ROOM											
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34

MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
						2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
Net Floor Area											295.41
Total Net Floor Area											295.41
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				413.5796	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				551.44
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:						562.4683	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				562.47

Table 3.2.5 Architecture Programming of Yoga and Gym Building

ARCHITECTURAL PROGRAMMING											
ARCHITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:		FOOD STALLS AND COMMERCIAL STALL									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s	Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal	
					Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture		
RENTABLE STALLS	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	39.2	8	16	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	11.52	50.72
	10	VISITORS	0.98	78.4	8	8	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	11.2	89.60
			0.98	0		16	KITCHEN SINK	0.6	0.5	4.8	4.80
			0.98	0		20	TABLE	0.8	0.8	12.8	12.80
			0.98	0		80	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	20	20.00
STORAGE	2	EMPLOYEES	0.98	11.76	6	16	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	11.52	23.28
PUBLIC TOILET	14	VISITORS	0.98	13.72	1	14	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	3.36	17.08
				0		14	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	4.2	4.20
UTILITIES											
ELECTRICAL A54: O57 ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90

					0		2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
											Net Floor Area	242.50
											Total Net Floor Area	242.50
Circulation:		40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:		339.5	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:					452.67	
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:					461.72	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)					461.72	
SOUVENIR SHOP		5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	COUNTER	4	0.6	2.4	7.30
		20	VISITORS	0.98	19.6		5	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	3.6	23.20
				0.98	0		2	DISPLAY RACK	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
STORAGE		2	EMPLOYEES	0.98	1.96		5	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	3.6	5.56
EMPLOYEES LOUNGE		5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9		1	TABLE	0.8	0.8	0.64	5.54
					0		5	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	1.25	1.25
					0		1	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72
					0		1	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	1.4	1.40
					0		1	KITCHEN SINK	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.30
							1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	0.24
							1	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.30
RETAIL SHOP		5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	9.8	2	2	COUNTER	4	0.6	4.8	14.60
		40	VISITORS	0.98	78.4	2	10	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	7.2	85.60
EMPLOYEES LOUNGE		5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	9.8	2	2	TABLE	0.8	0.8	1.28	11.08
					0		10	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	2.5	2.50
					0		2	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
					0		2	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	2.8	2.80
					0		2	KITCHEN SINK	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.60
					0		2	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.48	0.48
					0		2	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.60
MANAGERS OFFICE		1	MANAGER	0.98	1.96	2	2	TABLE	1.2	0.8	1.92	3.88
		5	VISTORS	0.98	4.9		6	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	1.5	6.40
				0.98	0		2	SOFA SET	2	1	4	4.00

STORAGE		3	EMPLOYESS	0.98	5.88	2	8	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	5.76	11.64
UTILITIES												
ELECTRICAL ROOM		5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MECHANICAL ROOM		5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MAINTENANCE ROOM		5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
							2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
Net Floor Area												212.89
Total Net Floor Area												212.89
Circulation:		40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				298.046	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				397.39
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:						405.3426	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				405.34	

Table 3.2.6 Architecture Programming of Food Stalls and Commercial Stalls

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:	COFFEE SHOP										
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s	Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal	
					Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture		
COUNTER	5	STAFF	0.98	4.9	1	1	COUNTER	4	0.6	2.4	7.30
	1	MANAGER	0.98	0.98		2	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	1.44	2.42
						1	DISPLAY RACK	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72
KITCHEN	4	EMPLOYEES	0.98	3.92	1	1	AISLE TABLE	4	1	4	7.92
			0.98	0		6	RACKS	1.2	0.6	4.32	4.32
			0.98	0		2	RANGE	0.75	0.65	0.975	0.98
			0.98	0		1	DISHWASHING SINK	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72
STORAGE	4	EMPLOYEES	0.98	3.92	2	3	SHELVES	2	1	6	9.92
DINING AREA (INDOOR)	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	10	TABLES	0.8	0.8	6.4	11.30
	30	VISITORS	0.98	29.4		30	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	7.5	36.90
ALFRESCO	30	VISITORS	0.98	29.4	1	10	TABLES	0.8	0.8	6.4	35.80

			0.98	0		30	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	7.5	7.50
MANAGERS OFFICE	1	MANAGER	0.98	0.98	1	1	TABLE	1.2	0.8	0.96	1.94
	5	VISTORS	0.98	4.9		3	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	0.75	5.65
			0.98	0		1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	2.00
EMPLOYEES LOUNGE	10	EMPLOYEES	0.98	9.8	1	1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	11.80
			0.98	0		1	TABLE	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72
			0.98	0		1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	0.24
			0.98	0		1	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.30
PUBLIC TOILET	2	VISITORS	0.98	1.96	1	2	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.48	2.44
				0		2	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.60
WASH AREA	4	VISITORS	0.98	3.92		4	SINK	0.5	0.5	1	4.92
UTILITY ROOM											
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
						2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
Net Floor Area											176.43
Total Net Floor Area											176.43
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				246.995	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				329.33
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+							TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				335.91
WALLS:						335.9132					

Table 3.2.7 Architecture Programming of Coffee Shop

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:		OBSTACLE COURSE AND TEAM BUILDING AREA									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s		Area needed	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal
						Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment,	Length	Width	of	
PAVILION	70	VISITORS	0.98	68.6	1	70	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	17.5	86.10
TIRE OBSTACLES	5	USER	0.98	4.9	1	40	TIRES	0.4	0.4	6.4	11.30
NET OBSTACLES	5	USER	0.98	4.9	1	2	NET COURSE	5	3	30	34.90
BALANCE DISC	5	USER	0.98	4.9	1	2	BALANCE DISC COURSE	3	1	6	10.90
ZIGZAG BALANCE BEAM	5	USER	0.98	4.9	1	2	BALNCE BEAM	4	1	8	12.90
WALL OBSTACLE	5	USER	0.98	4.9	1	2	WALL OBSTACLE	1	1	2	6.90
OVER UNDER HURDLES	5	USER	0.98	4.9	1	2	HURDLES	0.5	1.5	1.5	6.40
NET AND SLIDE	5	USER	0.98	4.9	1	1	NET COURSE	3	5	15	19.90
			0.98	0	1	1	SLIDE	3	5	15	15.00
NET ARMY CRAWLS	5	USER	0.98	4.9	1	2	NET COURSE	6	5	60	64.90
EQUIPMENT STORAGE	5	PEOPLE	0.98	4.9	1	5	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	3.6	8.50
TOILET AND SHOWER	30	PEOPLE	0.98	29.4	1	15	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	3.6	33.00
			0.98	0	1	15	SHOWER	1	0.7	10.5	10.50
			0.98	0	1	8	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	2.4	2.40
GAZEBO	30	PEOPLE	0.98	29.4	1	30	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	7.5	36.90
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	PEOPLE	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
						2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
Net Floor Area											367.84
Total Net Floor Area											367.84
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				514.976	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				686.63
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:					700.3674	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				700.37	

Table 3.2.8 Architecture Programming of Obstacle Course and Team Building Area

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:		MULTI PURPOSE PAVILION AND PRIVATE FUNCTION HALL									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s	Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal	
					Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture		
NAME OF AREA:		MUTI PUPOSE HALL AND BANQUET HALL									
PAVILION	70 VISITORS	0.98	68.6	1	70	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	17.5	86.10	
			0		20	TABLES	1.2	1.2	28.8	28.80	
STAGE	15 VISITORS	0.98	14.7	1	1	BACKDROPS	2	0.6	1.2	15.90	
BACKSTAGE	15 VISITORS	0.98	14.7	1	1	TECHBOOTH	2	2	4	18.70	
			0		15	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	3.75	3.75	
CHANGING ROOMS	6 VISITORS	0.98	5.88	1						5.88	
PUBLIC TOILET (MULTI PURPOSE)	14 VISITORS	0.98	13.72	1	10	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	3	16.72	
		0.98	0		14	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	3.36	3.36	
STORAGE	2 EMPLOYEES	0.98	1.96		5	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	3.6	5.56	
UTILITIES											
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5 EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34	
MECHANICAL ROOM	5 EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34	
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5 EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90	
					2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44	
										Net Floor Area	204.79
										Total Net Floor Area	204.79
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:			286.706	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				382.27	
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:					389.9202	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				389.92	

Table 3.2.9 Architecture Programming of Multi-Purpose Pavilion

PRIVATE FUNCTION HALL											
NAME OF AREA:											
HALL	30	VISITORS	0.98	29.4	1	10	TABLES	1.2	1.2	14.4	43.80
				0		30	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	7.5	7.50
KITCHEN	5	PEOPLE	0.98	4.9	1	1	AISLE TABLE	4	1	4	8.90
			0.98	0		2	RACKS	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
			0.98	0		2	RANGE	0.75	0.65	0.975	0.98
			0.98	0		2	DISHWASHING SINK	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
PUBLIC TOILET	6	VISITORS	0.98	5.88	1	6	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	1.8	7.68
			0.98	0		6	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	1.44	1.44
MINI LIVING ROOM	10	VISITOR	0.98	9.8	1	2	SOFA SET	2	1	4	13.80
			0.98	0		1	TABLE	1.2	0.8	0.96	0.96
TOILET AND BATH	1	VISITOR	0.98	0.98	1	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	1.22
						1	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.30
POOL AREA	30	VISITORS	0.98	29.4	1	1	POOL AREA	7	7	49	78.40
			0.98	0		8	LOUNGER	2	0.7	11.2	11.20
				0		1	CABANAS	2	2	4	4.00
SHOWER AREA	6	VISITORS	0.98	5.88	1	6	SHOWER	1	0.8	4.8	10.68
STORAGE	2	EMPLOYEES	0.98	1.96		5	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	3.6	5.56
UTILITIES											
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
						2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
Net Floor Area											219.32
Total Net Floor Area											219.32
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				307.041	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				409.39
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:						417.5758	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				417.58

Table 3.2.10 Architecture Programming of Private Function Hall

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:		MINI OPEN THEATRE									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s		Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal
						Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture	
THEATRE	10	PERFORMERS	0.98	9.8	1	50	SEATS	0.5	0.5	12.5	22.30
	60	VISITORS	0.98	58.8		1	TECH BOOTH	2	2	4	62.80
						1	CENTER STAGE	10	10	100	100.00
Net Floor Area											185.10
Total Net Floor Area											185.10
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				259.14	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				345.52
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+WALLS:						352.4304	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)			352.43	
NAME OF AREA:		CAMPING SITE AND HIKERS POINT									
CAMPING SITE	60	VISITORS	0.98	58.8	1	30	TENTS	2	2	120	178.80
				0		60	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	15	15.00
				0		20	TABLES	1.2	1.2	28.8	28.80
SUPPLY AREA	10	VISITORS	0.98	9.8	1	6	RACKS	1.2	0.6	4.32	14.12
BRIEFING AREA	60	VISITORS	0.98	58.8	1	30	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	7.5	66.30
TOILET AND SHOWER	20	PEOPLE	0.98	19.6	1	10	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	2.4	22.00
			0.98	0	1	10	SHOWER	1	0.7	7	7.00
			0.98	0	1	8	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	2.4	2.40
Net Floor Area											334.42
Total Net Floor Area											334.42
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				468.188	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				624.25
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+WALLS:						636.7357	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)			636.74	

Table 3.2.11 Architecture Programming of Mini Open Theatre

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:	TERRA-FLORA AREA (GREEN HOUSES)										
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s		Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal
						Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture	
PLANT PROPAGATION FIELD	15	VISITORS	0.98	14.7	1	2	TABLE	0.8	0.8	1.28	15.98
(FRUIT BEARING)	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	10	PLANTING FIELD	5	1	50	54.90
			0.98	0		5	BENCH	1.2	0.6	3.6	3.60
VERTICAL FARMING	15	EMPLOYEES	0.98	14.7	2	10	HYDROPHONIC RACK	2	0.5	10	24.70
			0.98	0		10	HYDROPHONIC POLES	0.5	0.5	2.5	2.50
STORAGE AND EQUIPMENT ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	3	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	2.16	7.06
			0.98	0		2	EQUIPMENT BOX	1	1	2	2.00
NURSERY AREA	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	10	PLANTING FIELD	5	1	50	54.90
	15	VISITORS	0.98	14.7	1	5	BENCH	1.2	0.6	3.6	18.30
STORAGE AND EQUIPMENT ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	3	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	2.16	7.06
			0.98	0		2	EQUIPMENT BOX	1	1	2	2.00
WORKSHOP	15	VISITORS	0.98	14.7	1	2	TABLE	5	1	10	24.70
			0.98	0		15	CHAIRS	5	1	75	75.00
FLORA PROPAGATION FIELD	15	VISITORS	0.98	14.7	1	10	PLANTING FIELD	5	1	50	64.70
STORAGE AND EQUIPMENT ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	3	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	2.16	7.06
			0.98	0		2	EQUIPMENT BOX	1	1	2	2.00
PLANTS AREA (SHOP)	15	VISITORS	0.98	14.7	1	10	BENCHES	2	1	20	34.70
			0.98	0		5	TABLE	1.2	0.6	3.6	3.60
			0.98	0		10	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	2.5	2.50
			0.98	0		20	FLOWER POT AND VASES	0.5	0.5	5	5.00
			0.98	0		1	FOUNTAIN	3	3	9	9.00
			0.98	0		10	LARGE VASES	1	1	10	10.00
			0.98	0		1	WATER WELL	1.5	1.5	2.25	2.25
CISTERN	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	WATER TANKS	2	2	4	8.90
PUMP ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	PUPM	1	1	1	5.9
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90

			0.98	0		2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
Net Floor Area											455.65
Total Net Floor Area											455.65
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:	637.91	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:							850.55
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:			867.5576	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				867.56			

Table 3.2.12 Architecture Programming of Terra- Flora

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
HEALTH CARE											
NAME OF AREA:	HEALTH CARE					Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal
	Name of Space/Room	No of User/s	Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture	
EMERGENCY AND FIRST AID	5 STAFFS	0.98	4.9	1	10	CHAIR	0.5	0.5	2.5	7.40	
	10 VISITORS	0.98	9.8		2	TABLES	1	0.7	1.4	11.20	
		0.98	0		3	BED	2	0.8	4.8	4.80	
					2	SHELVES	1.2	0.6			
WASH AREA	2 VISITORS	0.98	1.96	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	2.96	
			0		1	SINK	2	0.7	1.4	1.40	
NURSES LOUNGE	5 STANDBY NURSES	0.98	4.9	1	1	TABLE	0.8	0.8	0.64	5.54	
			0		5	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	1.25	1.25	
			0		1	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72	
			0		1	COUNTERTOP	2	0.7	1.4	1.40	
			0		1	KITCHEN SINK	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.30	
			0		1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	0.24	
			0		1	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.30	
DOCTORS OFFICE	1 DOCTOR	0.98	0.98	1	1	TABLE	0.8	0.8	0.64	1.62	
			0		1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	2.00	
			0		3	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	0.75	0.75	

						2	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
ROOMS	2	VISITORS	0.98	1.96	1	2	BED	2	0.8	3.2	5.16
	2	NURSES	0.98	1.96		4	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	1	2.96
				0		2	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
PUBLIC TOILET	1	VISITOR	0.98	0.98	1	1	WATER CLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	1.22
			0.98	0		1	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.3	0.30
MEDICINE STORAGE (COLD AND DRY)	3	EMPLOYEES	0.98	2.94	1	3	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	2.16	5.10
UTILITY ROOM			0.98	0							
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
			0.98	0		2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
Net Floor Area											79.52
Total Net Floor Area											79.52
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				111.328	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				148.44
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:					151.4061	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				151.41	

Table 3.2.13 Architecture Programming of Health Care Building

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:		VILLAS (BALE SINUKUAN)									
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s	Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area subtotal	
					Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture		
MULTI FAMILY VILLA	50	VISITORS	0.98	49	1	10	SOFA SET	2	1	20	69.00
				0		10	TABLE	1.2	0.6	7.2	7.20
				0		50	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	12.5	12.50
				0		25	BED	2	1.2	60	60.00
TOILET AND BATH	10	VISITOR	0.98	9.8	1	10	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	3	12.80

				0		10	WATERCLOSET	0.6	0.4	2.4	2.40
				0		10	SHELVES	1.2	0.6	7.2	7.20
KITCHEN	3	VISITOR	0.98	2.94	1	10	COUNTERTOP W/ SINK	2	0.7	14	16.94
UTILITY ROOM			0.98	0							
ELECTRICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
MECHANICAL ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	6.34
PUMP ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	PUMP	1	1	1	5.90
MAINTENANCE ROOM	5	EMPLOYEES	0.98	4.9	1	1	SLOP SINK	1	1	1	5.90
			0.98	0		2	CABINETS	0.6	1.2	1.44	1.44
Net Floor Area											213.96
Total Net Floor Area											213.96
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				299.544	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				399.39
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+					407.3798	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				407.38	
WALLS:											
2 BED VILLAS	4	VISITORS	0.98	3.92	12	1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	5.92
				0		1	TABLE	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72
				0		4	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	1	1.00
TOILET AND BATH	1	VISITOR	0.98	0.98		1	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.3	1.28
				0		1	WATERCLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	0.24
						2	BED	2	1.2	4.8	4.80
						1	SHELF	1.2	0.6	0.72	0.72
KITCHEN	4	VISITOR	0.98	3.92		1	COUNTER W/ SINK	2	0.7	1.4	5.32
POOL	4	VISITOR	0.98	3.92		1	DIP POOL	3	2	6	9.92
Net Floor Area											29.92
Total Net Floor Area											29.92
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:				41.888	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				55.85
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+					56.96768	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				56.97	
WALLS:											
TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA * NO OF UNITS(12): (SQ. MTS.)										683.61216	

Table 3.2.14 Architecture Programming of Villas 1 and 2

FAMILY/BARKADA VILLA	8 VISITORS	0.98	7.84	5	1	SOFA SET	2	1	2	9.84
			0		2	TABLE	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
			0		8	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	2	2.00
					2	SHELF	1.2	0.6	1.44	1.44
TOILET AND BATH	1 VISITOR	0.98	0.98	5	1	LAVATORY	0.6	0.5	0.3	1.28
			0		1	WATERCLOSET	0.6	0.4	0.24	0.24
KITCHEN	5 VISITORS	0.98	4.9	5	1	COUNTER W/ SINK	2	0.7	1.4	6.30
					4	BED	2	1.2	9.6	9.60
Net Floor Area										32.14
Total Net Floor Area										32.14
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:			44.996	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				59.99
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:					61.19456	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				61.19
TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA * NO OF UNITS(5): (SQ. MTS.)										305.9728
HUT VILLAS	2 VISITORS	0.98	1.96	10	1	TABLE	1.2	0.6	0.72	2.68
					2	CHAIRS	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.50
					1	BED	2	0.9	1.8	1.80
Net Floor Area										4.98
Total Net Floor Area										4.98
Circulation:	40%	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:			6.972	TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				9.30
TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:					9.48192	TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				9.48
TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA * NO OF UNITS(15): (SQ. MTS.)										142.2288

Table 3.2.15 Architecture Programming of Villas 3 and 4

ARCHTITECTURAL SPACE PROGRAMMING: USER AND FURNITURE INVENTORY											
NAME OF AREA:	WHOLE SITE (KARINAN DE SINUKUAN)										
Name of Space/Room	No of User/s	Area needed per user	Total area of user	No. of unit/s	Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine					Floor area sub-total	
					Qty.	Name of Furniture, Fixture, Equipment, Machine	Length	Width	Total area of Furniture		
MAIN ADMINISTRATIVE BUILDING		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					713.56
MENRO		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					181.54
GALLERY AND RESTO		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					1574.62
WELLNESS SPA AND SAUNA		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					1137.58
WELLNESS GYM AND YOGA		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					562.47
FOOD STALL		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					471.62
COMMERCIAL STALLS		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					405.34
COFFEE SHOP		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					335.91
OBSTACLE COURSE AND TEAM BUILDING		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					700.37
MULTI PURPOSE PAVILION		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					389.92
PRIVATE FUNCTION HALL		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					417.58
NURSERY		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					867.56
MULTI FAMILY VILLA		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					407.38
HUT VILLA		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					142.22
2 BED VILLA WITH DIP POOL		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					683.61
FAMILY/ BARKADA VILLA		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					305.97
HEALTH CARE		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					151.41
MINI OPEN THEATRE		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					352.43
CAMPING SITE AND HIKERS POINT		COMPUTED				COMPUTED					636.74
										Net Floor Area	10437.83
										Total Net Floor Area	10437.83
Circulation:	40%		TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRUCLATION:	14612.96		TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/ EFFICIENCY:				19483.95	
			TOTAL FLOOR AREA + CIRCULATION/EFFICIENCY+ WALLS:	19873.63		TOTAL GROSS FLOOR AREA: (SQ. MTS.)				19873.63	

Table 3.2.16 Architecture Programming of Overall Development

3.2.1 DESIGN REPORT REQUIREMENTS

List of Structures

Administrative Building	
First Floor	Second Floor
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lobby • Information and Reception Desk • Waiting area • Public Toilet • Mini Bar and tables • Admin Office • Accounting Office • Central Security Office • Conference Room • Employees Lounge • Storage • Maintenance Room • Electro-Mechanical Room • Pump Room 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lounge Area • Storage • Entertainment • Toilet • Overlooking Balcony • Entertainment Area

Table 3.2.1.1 Administrative Building Space Requirements

MENRO (Municipal Environment Natural Resource Office)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information and Reception Desk • Waiting Lounge • MENR Officer Office • Conference Room • Kitchen • Private Toilet • Public Toilet • Bedroom/ Resting Area • Mini Living Room • Storage

Table 3.2.1.2 MENRO Space Requirements

Interactive Gallery and Resto	
Interactive Gallery (First Floor)	Resto (Second Floor)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lobby • Elevator • Display Areas <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Miniature of Mt. Arayat - Model Of Species of Plants - Sinukuan Statue • Curator Office • Storage • Public Toilet • Mini Library • Information Desk • Maintenance Room • Electro- Mechanical Room • Pump Room • Admin Office • Employees Lounge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Counter • Kitchen • Storage (Dry and Cold) • Chefs' office • Indoor Dining • Alfresco Dining • Employees Lounge • Public Toilet • Wash Area • Maintenance Room • Electro-Mechanical Room • Elevator

Table 3.2.1.3 Space Requirement of Interactive Gallery and Resto

FOOD PARK AND COMMERCIAL STALLS		
Food Stalls	Coffee Shop	Commercial Stalls
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rentable Stalls <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mini Kitchen - Storage • Utilities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintenance room - Electrical Room - Public Toilet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Counter • Display Area • Dining Area • Kitchen • Storage (Dry and Cold) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Souvenir Shop - Counter - Display Area - Storage - Employee's Lounge

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manager’s Office • Employees Lounge • Electrical Room • Public Toilet • Utility Room 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retail Shop • Counter • Display Area • Storage • Employee’s Lounge • Gift Shops • Public Toilet • Electro-Mechanical Room • Delivery Dock • Maintenance Room
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Table 3.2.1.4 Space Requirements of Food Park and Commercial

HEALTH AND WELLNESS BUILDINGS		
Spa and Sauna	Health Care	Gym And Yoga
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management Office • Counter • Waiting Lounge • Employees Lounge • Managers Office • Public Toilet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency and First Aid Building • First Aid Area • Nurse Lounge • Doctors Office 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gym Activity Area - Locker Areas - Shower Rooms - Toilets - Mini Pantry

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage • Foot Spa Area • Wash Area • Spa Rooms (Huts) • Spa Rooms (Deluxe) • Mini Pool and Relaxation Area • Bar and Tables • Sauna Huts • Shower and lockers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resting Area • Medicine Storage • Washing Area • Public Toilet • Utility Room • Electro-Mechanical Room 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yoga Activity Area • Locker Area • Shower • Equipment Storage • Pump Room • Electro-Mechanical Room • Equipment Storage
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Table 3.2.1.5 Space Requirements of Health and Wellness Building

MULTI-PURPOSE PAVILION AND PRIVATE FUNCTION HALL	
Multi- Purpose Pavilion	Private Function Hall
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage • Back stage • Changing rooms • Public Toilet • Storage • Activity Area • Electro- Mechanical Room • Utility Room 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hall • Stage • Backstage • Storage • Electro-Mechanical Room • Utility Room • Toilet • Living area with Mini-Kitchen • Public-Toilet • Pool area • Shower Area

Table 3.2.1.6 Space Requirements of Multi-Purpose Pavilion and Function Hall

OBSTACLE COURSE AND TEAM BUILDING AREA	
Obstacle Course for Functional Fitness	Auxiliary Structure
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tires Obstacle • Net climb obstacle • Balance Disc • Wall obstacle • Zigzag Balance Beam • Over under Hurdles • Net and slide • Net Army Crawl • Wall Climbing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment storage • Shower Area • Public Toilet • Gazebo/ pavilion • Utility Room

Table 3.2.1.7 Space Requirements of Obstacle Course and Team Building Area

CAMPING SITE AND HIKERS POINT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Camping Area • Equipment and Supply Room • Toilet and Shower • Briefing area

Table 3.2.1.8 Space Requirements of Camping Site and Hikers Point

TERRA -AVIARY AREA		
Plant Propagation	Nursery	Butterfly Garden
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage • Planting fields (vegetables and Fruits) • Equipment Room 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage • Planting areas (for Trees and Big plants) • Workshop • Equipment Room 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage • Flora Propagation • Equipment Room

Table 3.2.1.9 Space Requirements of Terra -Aviary Area

VILLAS		
Individual Huts (1 bed)	Villa 2 (2 bed) with Mini Pool	Multi Family Villas (2 and 1 bedroom per unit)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 bed • Communal Toilet and Bath 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 beds • Dip pool • Toilet and bath • Mini kitchen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 bed Unit - Kitchen and T & B • 2 bed unit - Kitchen and T & B • Maintenance Room • Electro-Mechanical Room • Pump Room

Table 3.2.1.10 Space Requirements of Villas

POOL AND CABANAS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Swimming pools • Bar and Drinks Area - Bar Counter - Storage - Lounge • Cabanas and Cottages • Shower Rooms • Public Toilets

- Pump Rooms
- Water Reservoir

Table 3.2.1.11 Space Requirements of Pool and Cabanas

ACTIVITY AREAS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerial Cycling and Zipline <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Viewing Deck - Tower - Briefing Area - Equipment Area - Ticket Booth • Zen Garden <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gazebo - Sensory Attractions - Mini Ponds • Park and Playground • Jogging and Cycling Area <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Bicycle Renting Area • Mini Thrust Theatre • Outdoor Sports Spaces

Table 3.2.1.12 Space Requirements of Activity Areas

3.3 DESIGN STANDARDS AND LAWS AFFECTING THE PROJECT

EXISTING LAWS

- **PRESIDENTIAL DECREE (P.D.) NO. 1096**

ADOPTING A NATIONAL BUILDING CODE OF THE PHILIPPINES (NBCP)

THEREBY REVISING REPUBLIC ACT NUMBERED SIXTY-FIVE HUNDRED

FORTY-ONE (R.A. NO. 6541)

It is hereby declared to be the policy of the State to safeguard life, health, property, and public welfare, consistent with the principles of sound environmental management and control; and to this end, make it the purpose of this Code to provide for all buildings and structures, a framework of minimum standards and requirements to regulate and control their location, site, design quality of materials, construction, use, occupancy, and maintenance.

- **BP344- ACCESSIBILITY LAW**

“AN ACT TO ENHANCE THE MOBILITY OF DISABLED PERSONS BY REQUIRING CERTAIN BUILDINGS, INSTITUTIONS, ESTABLISHMENTS AND PUBLIC UTILITIES TO INSTALL FACILITIES AND OTHER DEVICES”

- **REPUBLIC ACT No. 9514**

“AN ACT ESTABLISHING A COMPREHENSIVE FIRE CODE OF THE PHILIPPINES, REPEALING PRESIDENTIAL DECREE NO. 1185 AND FOR OTHER PURPOSES”

- **REPUBLIC ACT NO. 9593**

“AN ACT DECLARING A NATIONAL POLICY FOR TOURISM AS AN ENGINE OF INVESTMENT, EMPLOYMENT, GROWTH AND NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT, AND STRENGTHENING THE DEPARTMENT OF TOURISM AND ITS ATTACHED AGENCIES TO EFFECTIVELY AND EFFICIENTLY IMPLEMENT THAT POLICY, AND APPROPRIATING FUNDS THEREFOR”.

The State declares tourism as an indispensable element of the national economy and an industry of national interest and importance, which must be harnessed as an engine of socio-economic growth and cultural affirmation to generate investment, foreign exchange, and employment, and to continue to mold an enhanced sense of national pride for all Filipinos.

- **RULES AND REGULATIONS TO GOVERN THE ACCREDITATION OF HOTELS, TOURISTS INNS, MOTELS, APARTELS, RESORTS, PENSION HOUSES AND OTHER ACCOMMODATION ESTABLISHMENTS**

Pursuant to the provisions of Executive Order no. 120 in relation to Republic Act no.7160, otherwise known as the Local Government Code of 1991 on the devolution of DOT's regulatory function over tourist establishments, the following rules and regulations to govern the accreditation of accommodation establishments are hereby promulgated.

A. STANDARDS

BUILDING HEIGHT LIMIT

BUILDING HEIGHT COMPARISON		
Building/ Structure Use	NBCP (PD 1096)	DAO 2009-09
Parks and Open Recreational and Entertainment Spaces	15 meters (or must complement the duly-approved BHL in the Major zone it is part of)	10 meters

Table 3.3.1 Building Height Comparison

PARKING

Specific Uses or of Occupancy (refer to Section 1.3 of this Rule)	Reference Uses or Character of Occupancies or Type of Buildings/Structures	Minimum Required Parking Slot, Parking Area and Loading Space Requirements
8. GROUP H		
8.1. Division H-1	Public recreational assembly buildings such as theaters/cinemas, auditoria, etc.	One (1) car slot and one (1) <i>jeepney</i> /shuttle slot for every 50.00 sq. meters of spectator area; and one (1) bus parking slot for every two hundred (200) spectators
8.2 Division H-2	Dance halls, cabarets, ballrooms, skating rinks and cockfighting arenas, etc.	-do-
8.3 Division H-3	Dance halls, ballrooms, skating rinks, etc.	-do-
8.4 Division H-4	Covered amusement parks, amusement and entertainment complexes, etc.	one (1) car slot for every 50.00 sq. meters of gross floor area
	Clubhouses, beach houses and the like	one (1) slot for every 100.00 sq. meters of gross floor area
9. GROUP I		
9.1. Division I-1	Recreational or similar public assembly buildings such as stadia, sports complexes, convention centers, etc.	One (1) car slot and one (1) <i>jeepney</i> /shuttle slot for every 50.00 sq. meters of spectator area; and one (1) bus parking slot for every two hundred (200) spectators.
10. GROUP J		
10.1. Division J-1	Agriculture-related uses or occupancies (A)	Not required if located outside urbanized area; if located within urbanized area, provide one (1) car slot for every 1,000.00 sq. meters of gross floor area and one (1) bus slot for every one hundred (100) workers; if number of workers exceed two hundred (200), provide one (1) off-RROW (or off-street) passenger loading space that can accommodate two (2) queued <i>jeepney</i> /shuttle slots; provide at least one (1) loading slot for articulated truck or vehicle

Table 3.3.2 Parking for Recreational Use Structures

MIXED OCCUPANCY

SECTION 703. Mixed Occupancy

(a) General Requirements

When a building is of mixed occupancy or used for more than one occupancy, the whole building shall be subject to the most restrictive requirement pertaining to any of the type of occupancy found therein except in the following:

(1) When a one-storey building houses more than one occupancy, each portion of the building shall conform to the requirement of the particular occupancy housed therein and;

(2) Where minor accessory uses do not occupy more than ten percent of the area of any floor or a building, nor more than ten percent of the basic area permitted in the occupancy requirements, in which case, the major use of the building shall determine the occupancy classification.

(b) Forms of Occupancy Separation

Occupancy separations shall be vertical or horizontal or both, or when necessary, of such other forms as may be required to afford a complete separation between the various occupancy divisions in the building.

WOODEN POST

The dimensions of Wooden Post shall be those found in Table. Each posts shall be anchored to such footing by straps of bolt and adequate size

Dimension of Wooden Posts or Suportales

Type Building	Maximum Height of 1st Floor (meters)	Maximum Height Total (meters)	Maximum Spacing of Post (meters)	Required Maximum Finished Size of <i>Suportales</i> (millimeters)
1-Storey Shed	-	4.00	3.50	100 X 100
1-Storey Shed	-	3.00	4.00	100 X 100
1-Storey Shed	-	5.00	4.00	125 X 125
1-Storey House or Chalet	1.00 - 3.00	5.50	3.60	125 X 125
2-Storey House	3.00	6.00	3.00	125 X 125
2-Storey House	4.50	7.00	4.00	120 X 120
2-Storey House	5.00	8.00	4.50	175 X 175
2-Storey House	-	9.00	4.50	200 X 200

Table 3.3.3 Wooden Posts Table

Logs or tree trunk suportales may be used as post in indigenous traditional type of construction, provided that these are such sizes and spacing as to sustain vertical loading equivalent at least to the loading capacities of the posts and spacing in this table.

ZIPLINE ROLLER COASTER

A Zipline Roller Coaster is an amusement ride where a rider sits in a cart suspended by a harness at the starting position.

Zipline Roller Coasters range up to 330m in length with an exact 360-degree loop.

Track height depends upon the zip line roller coaster, the smaller the roller coaster, the lower the height.

Average Height: 9.72 meters from the ground with an average running height of 8 meters.

The track's height also depends upon the speed of the ride due to the risk of danger, which is 21.5km/hour maximum. A huge zip line roller coaster can surge up to 150 feet, and a smaller one can surge up to 40 feet.

Average area required :1250 meters square with a track length of 250 meters.

However, the Zipline roller coaster area depends upon its track length. For example, a mini zipline roller coaster with 115 meters of track length consumes a space of about 500 meters square.

B. Computation According to NBC

Percentage of Site Occupancy (PSO)

Reference Table of Maximum Allowable PSO, Maximum Allowable ISA, the MACA, the Minimum USA, and TOSL by Type of Land Use Zoning Per Lot.

Table VIII.1. Reference Table of Maximum Allowable PSO, Maximum Allowable ISA, the MACA, the Minimum USA and the TOSL by Type of Land Use Zoning per Lot

Building/ Structure Use or Occupancy (or Land Use) _a	% of Total Lot Area (TLA)				
	Duly-Approved Zoning _b	Maximum Allowable PSO _{c,d}	Maximum Allowable ISA _c (Paved Open Spaces)	Minimum USA (Unpaved Open Spaces)	TOSL _d (ISA + USA)
Parks and Open Recreational Spaces	-	20	30	50	80

Table 3.3.4 Development Control Reference Table PSO

Allowable Maximum Percentage of Site occupancy for Parks and Open Recreational Spaces = 20 % of TLA

73, 964 sqm. X 20 % =14,792.8 sq. mts

Table VIII.1. Reference Table of Maximum Allowable PSO, Maximum Allowable ISA, the MACA, the Minimum USA and the TOSL by Type of Land Use Zoning per Lot

Building/ Structure Use or Occupancy (or Land Use) _a	% of Total Lot Area (TLA)				
	Duly-Approved Zoning _b	Maximum Allowable PSO _{c,d}	Maximum Allowable ISA _c (Paved Open Spaces)	Minimum USA (Unpaved Open Spaces)	TOSL _d (ISA + USA)
Parks and Open Recreational Spaces	-	20	30	50	80

Table 3.3.5 Development Control Reference Table ISA

Allowable Maximum Impervious Surface Area for Parks and Open Recreational Spaces = 30 % of TLA

73, 964 sqm. X 30 % = 22,189.2 sq. mts

Table VIII.1. Reference Table of Maximum Allowable PSO, Maximum Allowable ISA, the MACA, the Minimum USA and the TOSL by Type of Land Use Zoning per Lot

Building/ Structure Use or Occupancy (or Land Use) _a	% of Total Lot Area (TLA)				
	Duly-Approved Zoning _b	Maximum Allowable PSO _{c,d}	Maximum Allowable ISA _c (Paved Open Spaces)	Minimum USA (Unpaved Open Spaces)	TOSL _d (ISA + USA)
Parks and Open Recreational Spaces	-	20	30	50	80

Table 3.3.6 Development Control Reference Table USA

Allowable Maximum Percentage of Site occupancy for Parks and Open Allowable Minimum Unpaved Surface Area for Parks and Open Recreational Spaces = 50 % of TLA

73, 964 sqm. X 50 % = 36,982 sq. mts

Table VIII.1. Reference Table of Maximum Allowable PSO, Maximum Allowable ISA, the MACA, the Minimum USA and the TOSL by Type of Land Use Zoning per Lot

Building/ Structure Use or Occupancy (or Land Use) _a	% of Total Lot Area (TLA)				
	Duly-Approved Zoning _b	Maximum Allowable PSO _{c,d}	Maximum Allowable ISA _c (Paved Open Spaces)	Minimum USA (Unpaved Open Spaces)	TOSL _d (ISA + USA)
Parks and Open Recreational Spaces	-	20	30	50	80

Table 3.3.7 Development Control Reference Table TOSL and MACA

Total Open Space Within Lot (TOSL)= ISA +USA

ISA (30%) + USA (50%) = 80% OF TLA

73, 964 sqm. X 80 % = 59,171.2 Sq. Mts

Maximum Allowable Construction Area for Parks and Open Recreational

Spaces = PSO+ISA

20%(PSO) +30% (ISA)= 50% of TLA

73, 964 sqm. X 50 % = 36,982 sq. mts

C. DENR ADMINISTRATIVE ORDERS

REPUBLIC ACT No. 11038

An Act Declaring Protected Areas and Providing for Their Management, Amending for This Purpose Republic Act No. 7586, Otherwise Known as the "National Integrated Protected Areas System (NIPAS) Act of 1992" and for Other Purposes

Section 1. Title. - This Act shall be known and referred to as the "**Expanded National Integrated Protected Areas System Act of 2018**".

Section 2. Section 2 of Republic Act No. 7586 is hereby amended to read as follows:

"Sec. 2. Declaration of Policy. - Cognizant of the profound impact of human activities on all components of the natural environment particularly the effect of increasing population, resource exploitation and industrial advancement, and recognizing the critical importance of protecting and maintaining the natural, biological, and physical diversities of the environment notably on areas with biologically unique features to sustain human life and development, as well as plant and animal life, it is hereby declared the policy of the State to secure for the Filipino people of present for future generations, the perpetual existence of all native plants and animals through the establishment of a comprehensive system of integrated protected areas within the classification of national park as provided for in the Constitution.

❖ **Section 18. Section 20 of Republic Act No. 7586 is hereby amended to read as follows:**

"Sec. 20. *Prohibited Acts.* - Except as may be allowed by the nature of their categories and pursuant to rules and regulations governing the same, the following acts are prohibited within protected areas:

"(a) Poaching, killing, destroying, disturbing of any wildlife including in private lands within the protected area;

"(b) Hunting, taking, collecting, or possessing of any wildlife, or by-products derived therefrom, including in private lands within the protected area without the necessary permit, authorization or exemption: *Provided*, That the PASU as authorization or exemption only for culling, scientific research, the exemptions provided under Section 27(a) of Republic Act No. 9147 (Wildlife Resources, Conservation and Protection Act) or harvests of nonprotected species in multiple-use zones by tenured migrants and IPs;

"(c) Cutting, gathering, removing or collecting timber within the protected area including private lands therein, without the necessary permit, authorization,

certification of planted trees or exemption such acts are done in accordance with the duly recognized practices of the IPs/ICCs for subsistence purposes;

"(d) Possessing or transporting outside the protected area any timber, forest products, wildlife, or by-products derived therefrom which are ascertained to have been taken from the protected area other than exotic species, the culling of which has been authorized under an appropriate permit;

"(e) Using any fishing or harvesting gear and practices or any of their variations that destroys coral reefs, seagrass beds or other marine life and their associated habitats or terrestrial habitat as may be determined by the DA or the DENR; *Provided*, that mere possession of such gears within the protected areas shall be *prima facie* evidence of their use;

"(f) Dumping, throwing, using, or causing to be dumped into or places in the protected area of any toxic chemical, noxious or poisonous substance or nonbiodegradable material, untreated sewage or animal waste or products whether in liquid, solid or gas state, including pesticides and other hazardous substances as defined under Republic Act No. 6969, otherwise known as the "Toxic Substances and Hazardous and Nuclear Waste Control Act of 1990" detrimental to the protected area, or to the plants and animals or inhabitants therein;

"(g) Operating any motorized conveyance within the protected area without permit from the PAMB, except when the use of such motorized conveyance is the only practical means of transportation of IPs/ICCs in accessing their ancestral domain/land;

"(h) Altering, removing, destroying or defacing boundary marks or signs;

"(i) Engaging in 'kaingin' or, any manner, causing forest fires inside the protected area;

"(j) Mutilating, defacing, destroying, excavating, vandalizing or, in any manner damaging any natural formation, religious, spiritual, historical sites, artifacts and other objects of natural beauty, scenic value or objects of interest to IPs/ICCs;

"(k) Damaging and leaving roads and trails in damaged condition;

"(l) Littering or depositing refuse or debris on the ground or in bodies of water;

"(m) Possessing or using blasting caps or explosives anywhere within the protected area;

"(n) Occupying or dwelling in any public land within the protected area without clearance from the PAMB;

"(o) Constructing, erecting, or maintaining any kind of structure, fence or enclosure, conducting any business enterprise within the protected area without prior clearance

from the PAMB and permit from the DENR, or conducting these activities in a manner that is inconsistent with the management plan duly approved by the PAMB;

"(p) Undertaking mineral exploration or extraction within the protected area;

"(q) Engaging in commercial or large-scale quarrying within the protected area;

"(r) Establishing or introducing exotic species, including GMOs or invasive alien species within the protected area;

"(s) Conducting bioprospecting within the protected area without prior PAMB clearance in accordance with existing guidelines: *Provided*, That in addition to the penalty provided herein, any commercial use of any substance derived from nonpermitted bioprospecting within a protected area will not be allowed and all revenue earned from illegal commercialization thereof shall be forfeited and deposited as part of the IPAF;

"(t) Prospecting, hunting or otherwise locating hidden treasure within the protected area;

"(u) Purchasing or selling, mortgaging or leasing lands or other portions of the protected area which are covered by any tenurial instrument; and

"(v) Constructing any permanent structure within the forty (40)-meter easement from the high-water mark of any natural body of water or issuing a permit for such construction pursuant to Article 51 of Presidential Decree No. 1067: *Provided*, that construction for common usage wharves and shoreline protection shall be permitted by the PAMB only after thorough EIA."

❖ Section 20. Insert twelve (12) new sections after Section 21 of Republic Act No. 7586 to read as follows:

"Sec. 24. *Special Uses Within Protected Areas.* - Consistent with Section 2 hereof, special uses may be allowed within protected area except in strict protection zones and strict nature reserves. The PAMB may recommend the issuance of tenurial instrument subject to compliance to ECC and payment of corresponding user fee equivalent to five percent (5%) of the zonal value of commercial land within the nearest barangay or municipality where the project is located multiplied by the area of development plus one percent (1%) value of improvement as premium: *Provided*, That the activity shall not be detrimental to ecosystem functions and biodiversity, and cultural practices and traditions.

Table 3.3.8 Republic Act No. 11038

DENR ADMINISTRATIVE ORDER NO. 2009-09, August 20, 2009

STANDARD DESIGN AND SPECIFICATION OF SIGNS, BUILDINGS, FACILITIES AND OTHER INFRASTRUCTURE THAT MAY BE INSTALLED AND/OR CONSTRUCTED WITHIN PROTECTED AREAS

Pursuant to Section 10 (1) and (m) of Republic Act No. 7586, otherwise known as the NIPAS Act of 1992 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations, and Executive Order No. 111, "Establishing the Guidelines for Ecotourism Development in the Philippines," and all other laws/decrees, and to provide guidelines on the design and specification of signs, buildings, facilities, and other infrastructure within protected areas, this Order is hereby promulgated for the guidance of all concerned.

SECTION 1. Objectives. This Order shall have the following objectives:

1. To establish uniform signs for protected areas, including appropriate and distinctive symbols for each category in consultation with other concerned agencies;
2. To provide the designs and specifications including the materials to be used for buildings, facilities and any infrastructure within protected areas;
3. To set standards for the planning of ecotourism facilities within buffer zone and multiple use zone of a protected area and other ecotourism areas; and
4. To enhance visitor management program for ecotourism and conservation purposes.

SECTION 2. Scope and Coverage. This Order shall apply to all signs, buildings, facilities and any infrastructure that may be installed or constructed within multiple-use zone and buffer zone of a protected area and other ecotourism areas.

- ❖ The following are the different signs and infrastructure that may be allowed within the protected area;

2.2 Infrastructure/Facility

- a. Protected Area Information Center
- b. Entrance/Exit Gates
- c. Ticket Booth
- d. Guard Station
- e. View Deck
- f. Board Walk
- g. Lodging Facility/Cottage
- h. Toilets
- i. Parking Area
- j. Trails
- k. Camping Facilities

I. Materials Recovery Facility
m. Water pumps/catchment/facility

❖ **4.1 General Considerations** - In establishing uniform signs for protected areas, the following should be considered:

4.1.1 It should follow the standards of design, construction/installation and maintenance in the interest of public safety, convenience and good viewing such as those provided under Annex A [1] of this Order;

4.1.2 There should be harmonious and aesthetic relationship of all units;

4.1.3 The message should be limited to 10 items of information, especially on administrative, directional and restrictive signs.

❖ **5.1 General Considerations.** In designing and constructing any infrastructure for protected areas and other ecotourism areas, the following should be considered.

5.1.1 Infrastructure should comply with the following laws: P.D. 1096, the National Building Code of the Philippines, P.D.1586, "The Philippine Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) System Law", BP 344 "An Act to Enhance the Mobility of Disabled Persons by Requiring Certain Buildings, Institutions, Establishments and Public Utilities to Install Facilities and Other Devices," R.A. 7277, "Magna Carta for Disabled Persons," R.A. 386 "New Civil Code of the Philippines" and other applicable provisions of existing laws and local ordinances, including existing Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) if any

❖ **5.1.2 Design Requirements**

(i) In designing facilities and infrastructure consider minimal cost for operation and maintenance.

(ii) Any Infrastructure must integrate harmoniously with the natural and cultural environment. The natural contour of the landscape should not be significantly altered in the design of any infrastructure.

(iii) Flooring of vertical infrastructure shall be of suspended type and style, elevated by at least 1.00 m from the ground, for flat areas. The flooring shall adjust to the contour in the case of sloping ground. There shall be no alteration of ground contour to accommodate floors of structures on sloping ground.

(iv) The façade should blend with the surrounding area to complement the natural landscape. The emphasis on the design is that the structure should harmonize with the area and its cultural resources in proportion, color and texture.

(v) Architectural design should blend with the surroundings. It should adapt to the specific site and conditions.

(vi) Color used on exterior of the structures and facilities should blend, not contrast with the colors of the natural environment.

(vii) Major facilities should be placed only in appropriate management areas prescribed by the management plan and after consideration of carrying capacities.

(viii) The main characteristics of the landscape (site topography) should be recorded. The nature of site boundaries with the characteristics of adjoining development will determine the points of access to the site and will influence the road planning and laying out of infrastructure within the site. They will also determine the degree to which the site can be linked to or separated from adjoining development.

(ix) Any infrastructure should follow the policies on easements, i.e. they should be at least 40.00 m away from the highest high-water mark; 20.00 m. from the edge of the riverbank or 3.00 from the edge of any existing creek.

❖ 5.1.3 Construction and Installation

(i) Construction of high structures should be avoided. The maximum height of any building or structure shall be 10.00 m from the Natural Ground Line (NGL) to the roof top or highest part of the building/structure. Said structure should not interfere with the profile of the landscape.

(ii) Construction processes should combine traditional and modern technologies.

(iii) Excavation of septic tank, foundation/footings, compost pit and the like shall be limited to a maximum depth of 3.00 m below NGL.

(iv) New construction should, as much as practicable, take place in areas where infrastructure already exist or previously existed or in areas with degraded vegetation to avoid opening up of new spaces.

(v) The materials to be used should be indigenous, durable and fire resistant, however, concrete with simulated finish and steel reinforcement shall be considered when necessary.

❖ **5.2 Specific Considerations.** Basic facilities within protected areas are constructed to meet the needs of visitors but with minimum negative environmental impact. These structures should be designed in such a way that they are environmentally sensitive, practical and sustainable.

❖ **5.2.1 Protected Area Information Center.** The Protected Area Information Center shall be used as the Office of the Protected Area Superintendent (PASU) and Staff. It should have ample space for the following:

- (i) Office for PASU and Staff
- (ii) Reception area
- (iii) Display/exhibit area
- (iv) Audio-visual room (optional)
- (v) Utility area (laundry, kitchen, toilet and bath)
- (vi) Sanitary system

Specification:

- **Location.** The Protected Area Information Center should be constructed at a strategic point within the multiple use zone of the protected area, preferably near the main access points for easy reach of visitors and clients.

- **Size/Space.** The area of the building shall depend on its intended use and the number of the expected occupants. An ideal office floor area is 2.70 sq m (1.50 m x 1.80m) per staff. The size of the other rooms could be adjusted according to its use.

- **Classification.** Vertical structure

❖ **5.2.2 Entrance/Exit Gates.** There should be provision of entrance/exit gates to control the vehicles and pedestrians. Sally ports could also be provided for the gates. Security lighting should be provided if electric power is available.

Specification:

- **Location.** The entrance/exit gate should be located preferably at the boundary line of the protected area.

- **Size/Space.** The width of the entrance gate should be at least eight (8.00) m for two-way traffic. However, if the ticket booth would be placed in the middle of the entrance gate, the width of each lane should be 4.00 m at the minimum. If an arch would be constructed it should have a vertical clearance of 4.00m to 6.00 m.

- **Classification.** Vertical structure

5.2.3 Ticket Booth. The ticket booth is for the issuance of tickets to and, if necessary, collection of identification papers from incoming protected area visitors,

as well as collection of ticket stubs and return of identification papers to outgoing protected area visitors and clients.

Specification:

- **Location.** It should be placed along the entrance gate of the protected area after the guard station or in the middle of the entrance gate where incoming and outgoing visitors and vehicles can be easily monitored.
- **Size/Space.** A floor space of at least 2.70 sq m should be allocated for each ticket booth occupant plus additional space for cabinets, safe deposits boxes and lockers for the ticket collectors. The booth should be well illuminated and ventilated. Toilet facilities should also be provided.
- **Classification.** Vertical structure

5.2.4 Guard Station. The guard station serves as an observation post for security guards for incoming and outgoing protected area visitors. This should be properly lighted.

Specification:

- **Location.** The location of the guard station should be at a point where the guard can control entry and exit of pedestrians and vehicles, preferably at the entrance gate before the ticket booth.
- **Size/Space.** The size would depend on the number of expected guard/s on duty; allocating 1.50 m x 2.00 m per occupant
- **Classification.** Vertical structure

❖ **5.2.5 View deck.** A view deck maybe constructed to afford the protected area visitor a better view of a subject area or attraction.

Specification:

- **Location.** For protected areas with plain or flat terrain, the elevated or “tower” type view deck may be considered. For protected areas with hilly topography, the “veranda” type view deck is suggested so as not to alter the natural profile of the area.

- **Size/Space.** The recommended size of a “tower” or “veranda” type view deck will depend on the carrying capacity of the area; however, it should not be so big or too imposing as to attract attention to itself.

- **Classification.** Vertical structure

❖ **5.2.7 Lodging Facility/Cottage.** Lodging facilities or cottages are structures that are rented out to guest and visitors for overnight or extended stay within the protected area. The bed rooms could be for single or double occupancy or even multiple occupancy or dormitory type facilities. It should have provision for utility area either built-in for cottage type or detached for dormitory type.

Specification:

- **Location.** This should be placed at strategic locations but not in ecologically sensitive areas, accessible to protected area visitors via motor or animal-drawn vehicles or even on foot. It should have access to water and other basic utilities. Access to electric supply is optional.

- **Size/Space.** Minimum sizes of rooms and their least horizontal dimensions should be as follows:

For a plain cottage:	<p>-The living room should have a minimum area of 6.00 sq m.</p> <p>- Bedroom. There should be one (1) room for men and one (1) room for women, with a minimum area of 6.00 sq m per bedroom. A bath and toilet should have minimum area of 1.20 sq m.</p> <p>- Dining area and kitchen should have a minimum area of 3.00 sq m.</p>
For Dormitory Type (10-20 beds):	- The living room, common for both men and women should have a minimum area of 18.00 sq m.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bedroom. There should be one (1) room for men and one (1) room for women with a space allocation of 2.00 sq m per bed. - Toilet. There should be one (1) urinal, one (1) toilet bowl, one (1) lavatory and one shower separate from toilet bowl (optional) for every (5) men; and one (1) unit of toilet bowl, one (1) lavatory and one (1) shower separate from toilet bowl (optional) for every three (3) women. - Dining area should be 1.5 sq m per person. - Other rooms may be provided subject to the actual requirements as determined by the designer.
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- **Classification.** Vertical structure

❖ **5.2.8 Toilets.** The toilets should be with good water supply, illumination and ventilation. Sanitary system with two-chamber septic tank should be provided for cottages or lodging facilities that are not located in coastal areas. Cottages or lodging facilities located in coastal areas should be provided with three (3)-chamber septic tank.

Specification:

- **Location.** The toilet must be installed at strategic places within the protected area and accessible to persons with disability and should provide the comfort required by visitors.

- **Space/Size.** For a one (1) unit toilet, the minimum size is 2.00 m x 2.00 m. There should also be two (2) toilet bowls and one (1) lavatory for women's rooms; and one (1) toilet bowl, one (1) lavatory and one (1) urinal for the men's room. For differently-abled persons, wall mounted handrails (50.8 mm diameter stainless) should be

installed. Toilet units can be constructed in proportion to the number of expected visitors.

- **Classification.** Vertical structure

❖ **5.2.8 Parking Area.** The parking area is an allocated space intended for vehicles and other mode of transportation.

Specification:

- **Location.** Parking spaces should be allocated near the entrance gate or provided as adjunct to lodging facilities. Parking areas can be designated in other locations depending on the size of the protected area and if vehicles would be allowed inside.

- **Size/Space.** The regular space per parking slot is 3.20 m x 6.50 m and 3.70 m x 5.00 m for differently-abled persons. For bus and trailer-van, 4.0m x 15.0 m should be allotted. The overall length, width, height and minimum turning radius of the vehicle(s) should be considered.

- **Classification.** Horizontal structure.

❖ **5.2.8 Trails.** Trails should be designed for safe and convenient access, and as a means for environmental and cultural interpretation aside from other recreational purposes. It also directs foot traffic over a designated route away from ecologically sensitive areas.

The trail can be foot or a built-up trail. In areas where trails are present, it shall be maintained to avoid creating new trails. Introduce built-up trails for areas where there are heavy flow of visitors or heavy traffic.

The following factors should be considered in the establishment of trails:

- Attractions (views, wildlife observation, etc.) and sensitivity (least impact) should be the primary determining factors.

- It should also be offered for differing levels of physical ability, wherever possible.

- It should incorporate erosion and flood control in the design.

Specification:

- **Location:** The trails should preferably pass through natural places of attraction.

- **Size/Space:** Trails (both foot trail and built-up) should at the maximum be 1.50 m, wide enough for two people to walk abreast

- **Classification:** Horizontal structure

❖ **5.2.10 Camping Area.** Camping area should be provided where there are no lodging facilities or as an alternative for such facilities.

Some considerations in establishing camping area

- The area should be away from natural drainage system and not flood prone.
- It should be near or adjacent to toilet, laundry and kitchen facilities.

Specification:

- **Location:** variable depending on the other considerations
- **Size/Space:** Variable depending on the need
- **Classification:** Horizontal Structure

❖ **5.2.11 Landscaping.** Landscaping enhances the appearance of facilities and infrastructure as well as soften the overall impact of development.

Some considerations in landscaping

- The use of native perennial species of evergreen trees and shrubs and that can be more attractive and functional with age should be considered.
- Nursery should be provided to sustain the source of planting materials.
- The use of waste water from shower drainage and kitchen sinks should be considered for watering plants. This way, water is recycled and conserved.

Specification:

- **Location:** Where there is development
- **Size/Space:** Subject to site assessment or evaluation
- **Classification:** Horizontal structure

❖ **5.2.12 Solid Waste Management.** Solid waste management should be practiced to ensure the protection of the health of protected area visitors as well as the sanitation of the site. Possible options include provision of solid waste containers, Material Recovery Facility (MRF) for temporary storage of recyclable materials, and compost pit for biodegradable wastes.

(i) Solid Waste Containers. Solid waste containers (garbage receptacles) with cover should be placed where people pass through. These should be properly marked or identified as “biodegradable” (all capital letters in green), and “non- biodegradable” (all capital letters in black). Garbage from the containers must be regularly collected for recycling or composting of biodegradable.

(ii) Material Recovery Facility (MRF) should be installed depending on the threshold or volume of waste generated. It should be fenced and roofed with compartment for recyclable segregated materials.

(iii) Compost pit should be fenced and provided with cover.

(iv) Transfer or delivery of non-biodegradable to a properly managed site outside the protected area shall be arranged with the concerned local government unit.

Specification:

- **Location:** The MRF and the composting facilities should be located in areas not prone to flooding, far from water supply to prevent its contamination, and should be kept in such a way that it will not create an eye-sore.

- **Size/Space:** The size of MRF should depend on the volume of wastes generated inside the park; the diameter of compost pit should not be more than 2 meters; depth will depend on the volume of waste generated.

- **Classification:** Vertical Structure

Table 3.3.9 DENR Administrative Order No. 2009-09

DENR ADMINISTRATIVE ORDER No. 2007-17

RULES AND REGULATIONS GOVERNING SPECIAL USES WITHIN PROTECTED AREAS

Pursuant to RA 7586 otherwise known as the National Integrated Protected Areas System (NIPAS) Act of 1992 and its Implementing Rules and Regulations, the following rules and regulations governing special uses within protected areas are hereby promulgated:

Section 1. Basic Policy. The policy of the State provides for the conservation of biodiversity and sustainable development in protected areas to maintain essential ecological processes and life support systems. The effective management of protected areas should encourage cooperation between and among stakeholders to manage and develop the appropriate zones of protected areas through special use agreements.

Section 2. Objectives. This Order shall set forth in detail the guidelines for the processing and issuance of special use agreements within protected areas. Specifically, this Order shall have the following objectives:

2.1 To provide access and economic opportunities to indigenous peoples, tenured migrant communities and other stakeholders of protected areas thereby contribute in the reduction of poverty incidence;

2.2 To optimize the special uses of protected areas consistent with the principles of sustainable development and biodiversity conservation in cooperation with the stakeholders;

2.3 To guide the development of the appropriate zones of protected areas in accordance with their management objectives; and

2.4 To earn revenues for the sustainability of protected areas management:

❖ **Section 5. Kinds of Special Uses.** The following are the special uses, that may be allowed, but not limited to, within protected areas, subject to the issuance of an Environmental Compliance Certificate (ECC) and approval by the Secretary or his duly authorized representative:

- Ecotourism facilities
- Camp Sites
- Communication facilities

- Transmission lines
- Irrigation canals/waterways
- Rights-of-way (such as: transmission lines, communication facilities, etc.)
- Aqua culture
- Scientific Monitoring Stations (i.e. PAGASA, PHILVOLCS, etc.)
- Agro-Forestry Forest Plantation

Table 3.3.10 DENR Administrative Order No. 2007-17

TERMS AND CONDITIONS OF THE SAPA

The following are the minimum terms and conditions that the SAPA holder should observe and comply with:

1. Shall confine their development activities within the area specified in the Agreement.
2. Shall pay the users fee prescribed by the Management Board.
3. Shall, within six (6) months from the issuance of the Agreement, delineate and mark on the ground the boundaries of the area covered by the same under the supervision of the PASU. The SAPA holder shall preserve at all times such markers and other natural landmarks indicative of the boundaries of the area under the Agreement.
4. Shall protect the area from destructive activities including forest fires, illegal fishing, unlawful entry, and unauthorized gathering of resources, among others.
5. Shall submit to the PAMB an annual report of accomplishments indicating management and development activities undertaken in accordance with its Comprehensive Development and Management Plan (CDMP).
6. Shall not impede, obstruct or in any manner, prevent the passage of legitimate stakeholders and/or other protected area users and the public.
7. Shall secure prior approval of the PAMB on any changes in the management, ownership or capital stock of the company or corporation or transfer of a majority of the stock or shares of the company or corporation. Failure to do so without justifiable cause shall be sufficient ground for the cancellation of the SAPA.
8. Shall at all times comply with the conditions set forth in the ECC and permits for the project issued by other Government agencies.
9. Abandonment of the area or failure to exercise the privilege granted within the prescribed period of one (1) year from the issuance of the SAPA without justifiable cause.
10. The DENR and/or PAMB may impose additional terms and conditions in the SAPA, which are deemed, fit under the circumstances, consistent with the existing rules, laws and regulations.

SAPA Agreement formc7

Figure 3.3.1 SAPA Terms and Condition

ADMINISTRATIVE ORDER No.2013-19

**SUBJECT: GUIDELINES ON ECOTOURISM PLANNING AND MANAGEMENT
IN PROTECTED AREAS**

Section 2. Objectives. The general objective of this Administrative Order is to recognize and operationalize ecotourism for the conservation and sustainable use of natural resources in protected areas. It shall also have the following

Section 6. Ecotourism Planning and Management Process. The Ecotourism Planning and Management Process is divided into four (4) phases, namely:

1.Site Assessment. This phase will determine whether or not ecotourism management and development is the right strategy for the protected area. This consists of the following steps:

Checklist for Preliminary Site Evaluation (PSE)

It is recommended that the checklist be accomplished through a focused group discussion of people who are familiar with the situation in the protected area, and some resource persons from the tourism sector. This collective discussion will provide a better decision of whether to proceed to the ecotourism planning process

Guide Questions	Response	Remarks
Are there significant potential natural or cultural attractions in the area?	YES	Arayat National Parks is known for its fresh water falls and pools, topography and greeneries
Can visitor access to the attractions be easily established?	YES	National Highway is 5 mins away from the site with developed roads to resort
Can the attraction be protected at an acceptable level from the impacts of visitation?	YES	Resort is under a strict management

Is the area free of security problems and or natural hazards that cannot be effectively controlled by the management of the area of local authorities?	YES	Site is free from security problems with moderate hazard for natural disasters
Does the protected area have sufficient management and administrative authority to effectively manage implementation and monitoring of an ecotourism program at site level?	YES	Management office and Municipal Environment Natural Resources Office is situated in site.
Is there a reasonable expectation that initial funding needed to develop ecotourism will be available?	YES	LGU of Arayat are willing to fund the initial development of the project
Are the protected area managers, tour operators and communities willing to conform to ecotourism guidelines, i.e. low impact, small groups, impact monitoring, working with and actively involving communities?	YES	Operators are willing to conform
Will visitation improve biodiversity health or reduce threats to conservation targets?	YES	Activities like tree plantings are advised and portion of fund will be allotted for development of biodiversity.

Table 3.3.11 DENR Checklist for Preliminary Site Evaluation

DENR Administrative Order No. 2021- 11

SUBJECT: GUIDELINES IN THE PROCESSING AND ISSUANCE OF PERMITS FOR THE CUTTING, REMOVAL AND RELOCATION OF NATURALLY GROWING TREES

Section 1. Scope and Coverage This Order shall cover all applications filed by any person/entity for the cutting, removal and/or relocation of naturally growing trees, either in the public/forest lands or private lands, except those applications filed by the National Government Agencies pursuant to DAO No. 2018-16 and DAO No. 2020-06.

This Order shall not cover the trimming, pruning, cutting and removal of trees within power line corridors which no longer require to secure prior clearance or permit from, but with due notice to, the DENR Field Offices, pursuant to RA No. 11361, S. 2019. Further, the transport of logs derived therefrom shall require a transport permit consistent with existing rules and regulations.

Sec. 2. Objectives The objective of this Order is to streamline the procedures and approval process governing the issuance of permits for the cutting, removal and relocation of naturally grown trees within private and public/forest lands; and to come up with a consolidated policy to promote reliable and concise information in a usable and coherent manner.

CHAPTER 4

MATRIX DIAGRAMS

BUBBLE DIAGRAM

ARCHITECTURAL PLANS

CONCLUSIONS

4.1 MATRIX DIAGRAMS

ADMINISTRATION BUILDING (ASLAGAN BUILDING)

Figure 4.1.1 Administration Building Matrix

GALLERY AND RESTO

Figure 4.1.2 Gallery and Resto Matrix

COFFEE SHOP

Figure 4.1.3 Coffee Shop Matrix

APARTMENT TYPE VILLA

Figure 4.1.4 Apartment Villa Matrix

FAMILY VILLA

Figure 4.1.5 Family Villa Matrix

4.2 BUBBLE DIAGRAMS

Figure 4.2.1 Bubble Diagram of Whole Site

ADMINISTRATION (ASLAGAN BUILDING)

ASLAGAN BUILDING(ADMINISTRATION BUILDING)

GROUND FLOOR

SECOND FLOOR

SINAG ALAYA GALLERY AND RESTO

GROUND FLOOR MUSEUM

SECOND FLOOR RESTO

Figure 4.2.2 Bubble Diagram of Admin Building and Aslagan Building

4.3 ARCHITECTURAL PLANS

THE SITE

Figure 4.3.1 Site Analysis and Architectural Concept

ADMINISTRATION BUILDING

ADMINISTRATION BLDG.
GROUND FLOOR PLAN

A1
1 2 SCALE 1: 200 MTS

ADMINISTRATION BLDG.
SECOND FLOOR PLAN

A1
2 2 SCALE 1: 200 MTS

Figure 4.3.2 Administration Building Floor Plans

ELEVATIONS

Figure 4.3.3 Administration Building Elevations

PERSPECTIVES

Figure 4.3.4 Administration Building Perspectives

ELEVATIONS

Figure 4.3.6 Gallery and Resto Elevations

PERSPECTIVES

Figure 4.3.7 Gallery and Resto Perspectives

APARTMENT TYPE VILLA

A3
APARTMENT TYPE VILLA
GROUND FLOOR PLAN
1 4 SCALE NTS

A3
APARTMENT TYPE VILLA
SECOND AND THIRD FLOOR PLAN
2 4 SCALE NTS

Figure 4.3.8 Apartment Villa Floor Plans

ELEVATIONS

Figure 4.3.9 Apartment Villa Elevation

Figure 4.3.10 Apartment Villa Elevation

PERSPECTIVES

Figure 4.3.11 Apartment Villa Perspectives

SPA AND WELLNESS

A4
**SPA AND WELLNESS
GROUND FLOOR PLAN**
2 | 5
SCALE
NTS

A4
**SPA AND WELLNESS
SECOND FLOOR PLAN**
3 | 5
SCALE
NTS

Figure 4.3.12 Spa and Wellness Floor Plans

ELEVATIONS

Figure 4.3.13 Spa and Wellness Elevations

PERSPECTIVES

Figure 4.3.14 Spa and Wellness Perspectives

GYM AND YOGA

GYM AND YOGA
GROUND FLOOR PLAN
A4 / 4 5 SCALE NTS

GYM AND YOGA
SECOND FLOOR PLAN
A4 / 5 5 SCALE NTS

Figure 4.3.15 Gym and Yoga Floor Plans

ELEVATIONS

Figure 4.3.16 Elevations and Perspectives

COFFEE SHOP

A5
COFFEE SHOP
GROUND FLOOR PLAN
 1 4 SCALE NTS

A5
COFFEE SHOP
SECOND FLOOR PLAN
 2 4 SCALE NTS

Figure 4.3.17 Coffee Shop Floor Plans

PERSPECTIVES AND ELEVATIONS

Figure 4.3.18 Coffee Shop Elevations and Perspectives

COMMERCIAL STALLS

COMMERCIAL STALLS
GROUND FLOOR PLAN
 A5
 3 4 SCALE NTS

COMMERCIAL STALLS
SECOND FLOOR PLAN
 A5
 4 4 SCALE NTS

Figure 4.3.19 Commercial Stalls Floor Plan

MENRO AND HEALTH CENTER

A6 MENRO FLOOR PLAN
 SCALE 1/7 NTS

A6 HEALTH CENTER FLOOR PLAN
 SCALE 2/7 NTS

Figure 4.3.20 MENRO and Health Center Floor Plan

PERSPECTIVES

Figure 4.3.21 MENRO Perspectives

VILLAS

FAMILY VILLA
GROUND FLOOR PLAN
A6 SCALE 3/7 NTS

FAMILY VILLA
SECOND FLOOR PLAN
A6 SCALE 4/7 NTS

TWO BED VILLA
GROUND FLOOR PLAN
A6 SCALE 5/7 NTS

TWO BED VILLA
SECOND FLOOR PLAN
A6 SCALE 6/7 NTS

HUT VILLA
FLOOR PLAN
A6 SCALE 7/7 NTS

Figure 4.3.22 Villas Floor Plan

PERSPECTIVES

Figure 4.3.23 Villas Perspectives

4.4. CONCLUSION

Arayat National Park (San Juan banyo) indeed is one of the most prominent and leading resort in Arayat known by many local and outside of the community. The site offers great experience of wellness and one with nature that greatly helps for rejuvenation. The existing resort for the past years plays a great role in lives of Arayatenos as it is a go to place for recreation and fun. As time goes by, the resort has also turned gray with not much of improvement to the current site. As the site offers great topography and natural resources, it is really the ideal location for health and wellness projects that aims to aid one's health and mind. To conclude, the resort needs revitalization and redevelopment to attain the maximum and efficient use of the site.

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This certifies that the document titled “**Karinan De Sinukuan National Park- Integrating Wellness and Recreation in Redeveloping the Arayat National Park for Regenerative Architecture**” by Carl Christian M. Garcia is essentially clear of plagiarism, and was subjected to Turnitin Similarity review. Scanned and reviewed by the Research and Planning Office on May 14, 2025 with the following details:

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Emmanuel M. Bagtas, PhD, RN
Officer-in-Charge, Research and Planning

May 9, 2025

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This is to certify that the undersigned has reviewed and went through all the pages of the thesis entitled “**Karinan de Sinukuan National Park – Integrating Wellness and Recreation in Redeveloping the Arayat National Park for Regenerative Architecture**” by **Mr. Carl Christian M. Garcia**, and found it thorough and acceptable with respect to the set of structural rules that govern the composition of *sentences*, *phrases*, and *words* in the English language.

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